

Assessing the Relationship Between Energy-Efficient Renovations and Swiss Households Health: A Longitudinal Study from 2013 to 2023

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Abstract

This thesis examines the long-term health impacts of energy-efficient housing renovations in Switzerland using longitudinal data from the Swiss Household Panel (2013–2023). To address potential endogeneity in renovation decisions, instrumental variable methods are applied, using cantonal renovation subsidies as instruments. The analytical sample includes 4,381 observations corresponding to 1,968 individuals, with an average self-reported health score of 4.02, and around 53 percent of households having undergone window or door renovations.

The results show that renovations are positively associated with improved self-reported health after accounting for endogeneity. In the IV-Probit model, the coefficient of *renovated_windows* is 0.0062 and statistically significant at the 10 percent level, with a first-stage F-statistic of 17.25 exceeding the Stock–Yogo threshold. Average marginal effects indicate that living in a renovated dwelling increases the probability of reporting “very good” health by about 1.9 percentage points ($p \approx 0.059$).

Conversely, the analysis of respiratory illness yields inconclusive results due to a smaller subsample ($N = 181$) and weak-instrument strength ($F = 8.64$, $p = 0.114$). Overall, the study concludes that energy-efficient renovations enhance perceived health but show no robust effect on respiratory outcomes.

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List of Abbreviations

2SLS	Two-Stage Least Squares
CHF	Swiss Franc
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
FOEN	Federal Office for the Environment
FOPH / OFSP	Federal Office of Public Health / <i>Office fédéral de la santé publique</i>
FORS	Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences
IV	Instrumental Variable
NCD	Non-Communicable Diseases
PC / HH / PL / etc.	Variable prefixes in the Swiss Household Panel
SHP	Swiss Household Panel
SES	Socioeconomic Status
STATA	Statistical Software for Data Analysis
WHO	World Health Organization

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1. Introduction

The impact of housing conditions on public health has become a growing concern both internationally and within Switzerland. While a growing body of literature highlights the health benefits of energy-efficient renovations—particularly improvements in insulation, heating systems, and ventilation—Swiss-specific empirical evidence remains scarce. Most of the existing research focuses on environmental gains or energy consumption reductions, with few studies providing a quantified assessment of health impacts within the Swiss context.

The motivation for this study stems from both this gap in the academic literature and the increasing visibility of real-life cases in the media. One particularly alarming case in France gained national attention in 2023: a 27-year-old woman had to undergo a double lung transplant after developing a severe respiratory illness, which her doctor linked to prolonged exposure to mold in her subsidized apartment, that was very poorly insulated. The poor insulation of her apartment led to a higher risk of mold survival and accumulation and therefore, a higher risk of developing a respiratory illness. After a careful inspection, mold contamination was indeed found in her home, raising public concern about the health consequences of poor housing conditions, especially in vulnerable populations (Le Figaro Immobilier, 2023).

Homes that lack proper insulation and ventilation, particularly in colder climates, are more susceptible to mold development due to moisture buildup from condensation (OFSP, 2021). Switzerland is not immune to these issues. In 2025, several cases of mold-related health problems were reported in Geneva, often linked to aging, poorly insulated buildings (Blick, 2024). The Swiss Federal Office of Public Health (FOPH) officially recognizes that indoor mold can be harmful to health. According to the FOPH, 20–25% of the Swiss population may be affected by mold problems, a figure that highlights the magnitude of this issue at the national level (OFSP, n.d.).

In response, the Confederation has issued a detailed informational flyer aimed at helping citizens recognize problematic mold exposure and take appropriate action, including contacting their landlords (OFSP, 2021).

This presents a notable public health risk, as exposure to mold can lead to a range of health problems, including respiratory conditions, allergic reactions, and skin irritations. Despite the urgency of this public health concern and the clear presence of mold-related risks in the housing stock, there is still no quantitative study in Switzerland that evaluates the health effects of building renovations—on chronic illness, or the prevalence of respiratory illness like lung illness. This thesis seeks to fill that void by providing an econometric analysis of Swiss household data, assessing whether insulation, window, and heating system renovations lead to improvements in self-reported health and reductions in respiratory illnesses such as asthma and lung conditions. In doing so, the study also seeks to contribute valuable insights for public health, housing policy, and energy strategy at both local and national levels.

This thesis is organized into seven chapters. It begins with an introduction and a review of the relevant literature, followed by the formulation of the causal hypotheses and the overall research design. The data sources and methodological approaches are then presented, leading to the empirical results. Then we have the part of analysis of the results and a brief discussion.

The thesis concludes with a summary of findings, their implications, and a discussion of the study's limitations. Additional materials, including variable definitions are provided in the appendix.

2. Literature Review

2.1. International literature

A substantial body of international research has explored the intersection of housing conditions, particularly building renovations, and public health outcomes. These studies underscore the significance of energy-efficient renovations in mitigating health risks associated with poor indoor environments.

In the United Kingdom, Gilbertson, Grimsley and Green evaluated the Warm Front Scheme, a government initiative targeting energy efficiency improvements in low-income households. The study surveyed 3489 dwellings and households across five major urban areas (Birmingham, Liverpool, Manchester, Newcastle, and Southampton) over two waves in the winters of 2001/02 and 2002/03. Participants received new heating systems or significant heating repairs. The results showed that individuals living in cold homes were twice as likely to report poor mental health (Odds Ratio = 2.0) compared to those in adequately heated homes, even after controlling for age, gender, and socioeconomic factors. These findings underscore the significant health benefits associated with improving housing energy efficiency (Gilbertson, Grimsley, & Green, 2012).

Building on evidence from the UK context, similar health benefits of renovation have also been observed in China, where large-scale heating system upgrades have led to measurable improvements in air quality and public health. Zhao et al. (2021) conducted a large-scale study in China to assess the health and environmental benefits of clean heating renovations, launched as part of a national campaign since 2017. Focusing on a major prefecture-level city, the study combined household surveys, PM_{2.5} exposure measurements, and health impact assessments. The renovations reduced the share of solid fuels in heating from 96% to just 6%, and cooking with solid fuel dropped by 70%. As a result, ambient PM_{2.5} concentrations declined by 0.5–5.0 µg/m³ (averaging 2.4 µg/m³), while indoor exposure decreased by 4.2 µg/m³ (95% CI: 3.5–5.0). These improvements were estimated to prevent between 162 and 457 premature deaths annually. Moreover, the benefit-to-cost ratios ranged from 1.51 (95% CI: 0.73–2.59) to 3.06 (95% CI: 1.49–5.23), demonstrating substantial public health and economic gains. The study highlights the importance of carefully designed subsidy

policies to ensure equitable access to these benefits, particularly for low-income households (Zhao et al., 2021).

MacNaughton et al. (2018) extended the analysis to a multinational context by quantifying the health and climate co-benefits of buildings certified under the Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) program across six countries, including the United States, China, and India. Their study estimated that between 2000 and 2016, LEED-certified buildings in these countries prevented the release of 33 Mt of CO₂, 51 kt of SO₂, 38 kt of NO_x, and 10 kt of PM_{2.5}, which translated into \$5.8 billion in health and climate-related economic benefits (ranging from \$2.3 to \$9.1 billion). In the U.S. alone, the health-related gains were equivalent to avoiding 172–405 premature deaths, 171 hospital admissions, 11,000 asthma exacerbations, and over 37,000 lost days of work or school. These findings strongly support the integration of health considerations in energy efficiency policies, especially in developing countries where the benefits could be up to ten times higher (MacNaughton et al., 2018).

One mechanism to explain those improvements on health, could be the action of mold on the body. Mold forms in indoor environments when three key conditions are present: excess moisture, organic material (such as wood, wallpaper, or dust), and poor ventilation. Humidity from cooking, showering, or even breathing accumulates especially in poorly insulated homes, where warm, moist air condenses on cold surfaces like windows, walls, or corners. When this moisture is not effectively ventilated, it creates a suitable environment for mold spores to develop and spread. Once established, mold releases microscopic spores into the air, which can be inhaled and irritate the respiratory system.

Several studies have highlighted the connection between poor insulation and increased risk of mold development in residential buildings. For instance, a study realized by Kon examined different wall constructions and insulation materials across various climates and found that poorly insulated walls significantly raise the likelihood of condensation, thereby promoting mold growth due to elevated indoor humidity (Kon & Caner, 2022). Hence, renovations can help disrupt these conditions.

Thermal insulation reduces cold surfaces where condensation occurs, heating system upgrades maintain stable indoor temperatures that discourage moisture buildup, and most critically, replacing windows increases airtightness and energy efficiency, but must be accompanied by proper ventilation strategies.

When done properly, such renovation reduces indoor humidity and air stagnation—two of the most important environmental triggers for mold—ultimately eliminating its growth and breaking the chain between poor housing and chronic illness (Mendell et al, 2011). The World Health Organization (WHO) has identified indoor dampness and mold as significant contributors to respiratory problems, including asthma, allergic rhinitis, and other respiratory infections. WHO concluded that occupants of damp or moldy buildings face up to a 75% increased risk of developing respiratory symptoms and asthma compared to those in dry environments, during the redaction of the first indoor quality guidelines on dampness and mold (World Health Organization [WHO], 2009).

A comprehensive review found consistent associations between dampness or mold and a range of respiratory and allergic health effects, emphasizing the need for effective moisture control in buildings (Mendell et al., 2011). Concretely, mold spores are inhaled, they can trigger immune responses that lead to airway inflammation, especially in individuals with asthma or allergies. This immune activation involves the release of histamines and cytokines, causing bronchoconstriction, swelling of the airway lining, and increased mucus production—all of which exacerbate respiratory symptoms (Kraft, Buchenauer, & Polte, 2021).

In cases of prolonged exposure, even in non-allergic individuals, chronic inflammation of the respiratory tract can occur, potentially leading to conditions such as chronic bronchitis, hypersensitivity pneumonitis, allergic reactions, fatigue and immune dysregulation, especially in sensitive individuals. Moreover, certain molds produce mycotoxins, a substance produced by a fungus, which can damage lung cells and disrupt immune regulation. Vulnerable populations, such as children, the elderly, and immunocompromised individuals, are particularly at risk, as mold exposure can impair lung development or lead to severe infections. The exposed biological mechanisms underscore the importance of maintaining

dry, well-insulated, and well-ventilated living environments to protect respiratory health (Kraft, Buchenauer, & Polte, 2021).

These international studies provide a compelling rationale for further research into the health impacts of housing conditions, particularly in contexts like Switzerland, where empirical studies on this topic remain limited.

2.2. Swiss literature and contribution of this thesis

In contrast to the growing body of international literature linking housing quality and health outcomes, Swiss academic research on this topic remains limited—particularly in terms of quantitative and causal analyses. Most studies in Switzerland have focused on the environmental and energy efficiency aspects of building renovations, while the public health dimension has received comparatively little empirical attention.

A recent study by Galimshina, provides a notable contribution on the literature of building renovations by examining the environmental and economic impacts of energy-efficient renovations in the Swiss building sector. The authors found that replacing fossil-fuel-based heating systems with heat pumps or wood pellet systems, combined with innovative insulation materials, can reduce greenhouse gas emissions by up to 87% annually. While health outcomes were not the primary focus, the study underscores the importance of better insulation and ventilation—not only for environmental benefits but also for improving indoor air quality. These findings indirectly point to potential health co-benefits, particularly in terms of respiratory well-being and comfort in renovated dwellings (Galimshina et al., 2024).

Another relevant contribution is offered by S. Nick, in 2024, who presents a policy-oriented overview of the potential transformation of the Swiss housing sector toward energy efficiency. While the paper outlines important institutional changes and investment needs, it stops short of quantifying the direct health benefits that may result from these renovations. The absence of a detailed causal framework limits the paper's ability to inform targeted health interventions or policy evaluation (Nick, 2024).

Despite these valuable contributions, no known empirical study has yet quantified the direct impact of housing renovation on individual health outcomes in the Swiss context. While the

Swiss authorities acknowledge the potential health risks associated with mold proliferation in poorly insulated or inadequately ventilated residential buildings—particularly in relation to respiratory problems such as asthma and chronic bronchitis—these issues remain underexplored in academic research. This gap is striking given the country's significant investments in energy efficiency programs and its increasing attention to environmental health. Thus, a detailed investigation into the health effects of building renovations in Switzerland, with a particular focus on respiratory illnesses, appears both timely and necessary.

The Federal Office of Public Health (FOPH) has published multiple guidelines and official recommendations that implicitly acknowledge the health consequences of poor housing conditions (OFSP, 2021). In particular, the FOPH has emphasized the dangers of mold exposure, citing that 20–25% of the Swiss population is affected by dampness or mold in residential buildings.

These issues are especially prevalent in older or poorly insulated housing stock, where inadequate thermal insulation and ventilation create conditions conducive to moisture accumulation and microbial growth.

Despite these public health concerns and institutional awareness, few empirical studies have quantified the impact of mold or housing quality on health outcomes in the Swiss context. This represents a significant gap in the literature, particularly when compared to international studies that have identified strong associations between building conditions and respiratory illnesses, including asthma and chronic lung diseases.

Given the scale of public subsidies provided through national programs such as Le Programme Bâtiments—which allocated over CHF 3.6 billion in renovation incentives between 2010 and 2023—the lack of health-focused evaluations is notable. While the programme's environmental and economic impacts have been regularly assessed, its potential role in improving public health remains underexplored.

This thesis seeks to address this gap by providing the first longitudinal, econometrically robust analysis of the health impacts of building renovations in Switzerland. By using panel data from the Swiss Household Panel and merging it with canton-level subsidy data, this

study contributes a new layer of understanding to the broader discussion on energy policy, health equity, and housing conditions in Switzerland.

3. Hypothesis and research design

3.1 Part I – The Impact of Renovation on General Health

The first part of the thesis evaluates the effect of housing renovation on self-reported health and the prevalence of chronic illness, as shown in Figure 1. This analysis is conducted using longitudinal data from 2013 to 2021, drawn from the Swiss Household Panel. A central challenge in estimating this relationship lies in the potential endogeneity of renovation decisions: households who renovate may differ systematically in their health profile, risk tolerance, or socioeconomic position.

To identify a causal effect, this study adopts two key strategies:

(a) Controlling for Socioeconomic Status (SES)

Socioeconomic indicators—including age, sex and income—are controlled for in all specifications. These variables are strongly associated with both renovation behavior and health outcomes. For instance, wealthier households are more likely to afford renovation and to live in healthier environments, while lower-income households are disproportionately exposed to environmental health risks. By including SES controls, I reduce omitted variable bias from observable confounders. In Chapter 4.2.3 Control Variables I will explain the exact rationale behind this choice.

(b) Instrumental Variable: Subsidy Amount

To account for the possible endogeneity, I employ an instrumental variable (IV) strategy using the subsidy amount allocated by the Swiss federal program *Programme Bâtiments*. This instrument affects the probability of undertaking renovation, but—under the exclusion restriction—is assumed to affect health outcomes only through its effect on renovation. This approach follows a two-stage least squares (2SLS) structure, with the first stage predicting renovation status using subsidy amount, and the second estimating the impact of (instrumented) renovation on health.

Figure 1 – Relationship between housing renovation and general health

Note : Renovation is assumed to impact health, in special chronic illnesses prevalence, partly by reducing mold rate, which are known to cause respiratory illnesses. Mold acts as a mediating mechanism between renovation and health, but is omitted from the DAG for simplicity.

Thus, renovation is hypothesized to directly affect health, in particular the prevalence of chronic illnesses directly. However, both renovation decisions and health outcomes may be influenced by underlying socioeconomic status. Furthermore, there is also an issue of potential endogeneity that I will explain more precisely in the next chapter. To address potential endogeneity, I use the Subsidy Amount given by Le Programme Bâtiments as an instrument, which affects renovation decisions but is assumed not to directly influence health outcomes as chronic illness.

3.2 Part II – Renovation and Respiratory Illnesses During the COVID-19 Period

The second part of the thesis refines the health outcome of interest by focusing specifically on respiratory illnesses, such as lung disease (Figure 2). This section uses a restricted panel of

individuals observed during 2021–2023 to ensure comparability and control for mortality-related attrition during the COVID-19 pandemic.

In this framework, an additional challenge arises from health shocks related to COVID-19 infection, which may independently influence respiratory health. To isolate the effect of renovation from pandemic-related influences, this framework incorporates the following elements:

(a) Controlling for the shocks of COVID-19 Infection

As in Part II, SES that are proven to have an influence on health are included as a confounder. In addition, COVID-19 infection status is introduced as a control variable. Since COVID is both a direct risk factor for respiratory illness and potentially related to SES (e.g., crowded housing, occupation), I control for it explicitly and represent its influence in the DAG.

(b) Controlling for Attrition Bias from Excess Mortality

An important methodological concern in the second part of the study is the potential for attrition bias, particularly due to excess mortality and panel dropout during the COVID-19 pandemic. Between 2020 and 2021, the Swiss population experienced a significant health shock, with elevated mortality among people already suffering from some form of respiratory illness¹. In parallel, the Swiss Household Panel (SHP) data show a notable decline in participation, especially among vulnerable groups. If these dropouts are not random but systematically linked to health status or other unobserved characteristics, the estimation of renovation's impact on respiratory illness may be biased. Specifically, the health profile of the remaining panel may appear artificially improved simply because the most at-risk individuals are no longer observed—a form of survival bias.

To assess whether COVID-related attrition significantly changed the composition of the sample, a two-sample Kolmogorov–Smirnov test was conducted to compare the age distribution in 2019 (pre-COVID) with that of the balanced panel in 2023. The

¹ The evidence of this excess of mortality has been found, and it will be explained in the next chapter.

result was statistically significant ($D = 0.0197$, $p = 0.007$), confirming a shift in the age structure and suggesting that the post-COVID sample became younger and more resilient. Still, the average age remained relatively stable — 42.5 in 2019 vs. 43.1 in 2023 — suggesting that key demographic variation is still captured.

Figure 2 - Causal Framework II : The Effect of Renovation on Health (Respiratory Illnesses)

Note: Dashed arrows represent potential confounding or indirect pathways. COVID-19 infection is treated as a health shock controlled during 2020–2021. Subsidy amount is used as an instrumental variable affecting renovation but not directly health.

To mitigate the risk of attrition bias introduced by COVID-19, the analysis is restricted to a balanced panel of individuals who were consistently present in the 2021, 2022, and 2023 waves of the Swiss Household Panel. This restriction ensures that changes in respiratory health are estimated within the same individuals over time, thereby minimizing dynamic selection effects and strengthening the internal validity of the analysis.

However, this choice makes it difficult to fully capture the broader health impact of the pandemic period. Individuals in poorer health — particularly older people and those with pre-existing respiratory conditions — were more likely to die or exit the panel during the COVID-19 years. As a result, the sample used for the post covid analysis likely reflects a younger and more robust subset of the Swiss population compared to the precedent years of

non-pandemic. While the sample remains broadly representative demographically, it may understate the prevalence of certain health conditions — and by extension, may underestimate the true benefits of renovation policies. In this sense, the reported effects can be interpreted as a conservative lower bound of the actual impact.

Future research with broader samples and longer time horizons will be needed to assess the full population-level impact of energy-efficient renovations in the post-pandemic era — assuming, of course, that no new pandemic arrives to challenge our datasets all over again.

With this contextual and methodological groundwork established, the quantitative analysis now turns to testing two central hypotheses. These are designed to capture both the general and respiratory health benefits that may result from improved housing quality.

H1 – Housing Renovation Improves General Health:

Renovating housing—particularly through windows upgrades—is hypothesized to improve self-reported health outcomes. This effect is assumed to occur partly by reducing harmful environmental exposures such as mold or poor insulation, which are known to contribute to chronic illnesses.

H2 – Housing Renovation Reduces Respiratory Illnesses (e.g., Lung Disease):

Renovation housing through windows upgrades is expected to reduce the likelihood of respiratory illnesses.

4. Data

4.1. Data sources and sample construction

The primary dataset used in this study is the Swiss Household Panel (SHP), a longitudinal survey that has been conducted annually since 1999, but in our analysis the time frame studied goes from 2013-2021 for the first part and 2021-2023, for the second part. The SHP is managed by the Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences (FORS), based at the University of Lausanne, and is one of Switzerland's most comprehensive sources of socio-economic data. It is designed to follow individuals and households over time, allowing for the study of dynamics in living conditions, economic status, health, and housing.

For the purpose of this thesis, the SHP database provides both household-level variables — such as *housing conditions*, *renovation history*, *energy infrastructure*, and *income* — and individual-level variables — such as *age*, *sex*, *education*, *health status*, *chronic illness* and *covid infection*. The longitudinal nature of the SHP enables the analysis of changes in health outcomes in relation to housing conditions across multiple years, making it an ideal source for this type of study. The data used in this thesis were downloaded from the official FORS website².

The analytical dataset used in this thesis was built by combining two longitudinal files from the Swiss Household Panel (SHP), a first dataset³, which contains household-level information, and a second dataset⁴, which includes individual-level data. These files were merged by selecting only the variables relevant to the research question, as listed in Table 1 (see appendix). To facilitate the analysis, the variables were systematically renamed for improved clarity and consistency. The merge was possible by matching the individual identifier (*idpers*) and the year (*year*) across the two datasets.

These new names were designed to directly reflect the content of each variable and improve code readability throughout the econometric analysis.

² FORS – Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences, "Swiss Household Panel – Data," accessed February 25, 2025, <https://forscenter.ch/projects/swiss-household-panel/data/>.

³ *shplong_h_user.dta*

⁴ *shplong_p_user.dta*

Another database was also added into the final database, called `shp_covid_user.dta`. This is important to control for the external shocks like COVID-19. It is very important to acknowledge that while the majority of the variables were available from 2013 to 2021, a few of them, for example the variables related to asthma lung illness were only available from 2021-2023. The variable `condition_accomodation` was available from 2013 to 2023 and the variable related to COVID-19 infection only on one database for the period from 2020 to 2021. I merged this database into the final database by matching the year and the personal identification (`idpers`).

In parallel, I constructed a separate dataset⁵, which contains annual canton-level financial data on energy renovation subsidies distributed by *Le Programme Bâtiments*. It was possible to merge this data by matching the year and canton of this new database to the main database. The main variable of interest was the subsidy amount in Millions of CHF. The data for the years 2017 to 2023 were retrieved directly from the Excel file "*Série de tableaux 2021*", specifically from *Tab 2.1 Analyse (versements)*, available under the section *Rapport annuel 2021* on the program's official website. The data for earlier years (2013 to 2016) were collected manually from historical PDF annual reports. For example, the 2016 subsidy amounts were obtained from page 36 of the report titled "*Rapport annuel Volet A et B*" (Le Programme Bâtiments, n.d.).

All amounts were standardized to a common unit (millions of CHF) to ensure temporal and spatial comparability across cantons. After preparing the three datasets, they were merged into a single unified file⁶. In the first part of the source code⁷ a cleaning phase was carried out. This included removal of 129 '176 invalid responses, missing or lacking, as well as recoding of scales when necessary (for example a yes/no variable into a real dummy variable). To ensure the integrity of the dataset, non-informative or invalid responses such as "inapplicable," "does not know," or "no answer" were systematically recoded as missing values.

⁵ `subsidy_amount_complete.dta`

⁶ `temp_p_h_merged.dta`

⁷ labeled "*PART I: RECODING THE VARIABLES*"

canton	canton_label	year	subsidy_amount (millions of CHF)
1	AG Aargovia	2013	9.09
2	AI Appenzell Inner-Rhodes	2013	0.29
3	AR Appenzell Outer-Rhode	2013	1.13
4	BE Berne	2013	19.23
5	BS Basle-Town	2013	3.19
6	BL Basle-Country	2013	5.35
7	FR Fribourg	2013	3.99
8	GE Geneva	2013	4.35
9	GL Glarus	2013	0.69
10	GR Grisons	2013	4.86
11	JU Jura	2013	1.47
12	LU Lucerne	2013	6.94
13	NE Neuchatel	2013	2.19
14	NW Nidwalden	2013	0.72
15	OW Obwalden	2013	0.69
16	SG St. Gall	2013	11.33
17	SH Schaffhausen	2013	1.35
18	SO Solothurn	2013	4.82
19	SZ Schwyz	2013	2.35
20	TG Thurgovia	2013	4.75
21	TI Ticino	2013	4.86
22	UR Uri	2013	0.57
23	VD Vaud	2013	8.13
24	VS Valais	2013	5.56
25	ZG Zug	2013	2.18
26	ZH Zurich	2013	20.61

Figure 3 - Image of the database Cantonal Subsidies.

Image of the construction of the Cantonal subsidies database for the year 2013, used to apply the IV identification strategy. Source : Le Programme Bâtiments

The initial sample was about 344'678 participants. To assess whether the sample is representative of the reference population, I compare the distribution of respondents across standardized age groups with official population benchmarks, following standard practice in survey methodology to validate or invalidate the sample representativeness.⁸

This technique consists of selecting a reference characteristic — such as sex and age group— and examining whether its proportions in the sample align with those observed in official national statistics. For example, the variable sex was used to test whether men and women were equally represented. A slight deviation is expected, especially knowing that there's slightly more females than males in Switzerland. The number of women exceeds the number of men by approximately 1% (Federal Statistical Office, n.d.). To formally test whether the proportion of females differs significantly from the population proportion, I performed a one-sample proportion test. In our sample, 51.29% were women compared to 50.5% in the

⁸ Visual inspection is a first step to check the correct distribution of a sample, but further formal tests have to be performed in order to determine the suitability of a sample.

Swiss population. A z-test for proportions yielded $z \approx 1.80$, indicating that this difference is not statistically significant at the 5% level ($1.80 < 1.96$). Thus, the sample can be considered representative with respect to sex.

A similar comparison was conducted for the distribution of age groups. The results likewise showed no significant deviation from the average age structure of the Swiss population, suggesting that the sample in principle reflects the demographic composition of the country. The average age in the sample is 43.14 years, compared to 42.9 years in the Swiss population. A z-test for means yielded $z = 1.74$, which is below the critical threshold for statistical significance at the 5% level. This result indicates that the sample is representative with respect to age (Statista, n.d.). However, it is important to acknowledge the limitations of this comparison. A z-test evaluates differences in means only and does not account for potential discrepancies in other aspects of the age distribution, such as variance, skewness, or kurtosis.

For a more comprehensive comparison of continuous variables like age, the standard approach would be to apply the Kolmogorov–Smirnov (K–S) test, which compares the entire empirical distribution functions of two samples.

In this context, however, the K–S test is not feasible. This test requires access to individual-level microdata for the Swiss population or a detailed empirical cumulative distribution function (ECDF) — neither of which are downloadable on the official website of the Swiss Confederation. Publicly accessible statistics (e.g., Statista) typically provide summary indicators such as means, medians, or age-groups, but not the full raw data necessary to perform a valid K–S test. These do not allow for the reconstruction of the empirical cumulative distribution function required for the test.

Given that age is coded into ordered classes in the dataset from the OFS, the chi-square goodness-of-fit test is an appropriate and widely accepted method for evaluating whether the sample distribution of age aligns with the known population structure.

It allows us to statistically determine whether the observed differences are meaningful or consistent with sampling variability. I performed a Chi-square goodness-of-fit test comparing the observed frequencies across five age classes to the expected frequencies derived from OFS data. The test yielded a Chi-square statistic of 286.46 with 4 degrees of

freedom, and a corresponding p-value < 0.001 ($p = 9.02e-61$). This result is highly statistically significant, indicating that the observed distribution of age classes in the sample deviates substantially from the expected distribution. Therefore, I reject the null hypothesis that the sample follows the same age distribution as the reference population. This suggests that the sample is not representative of the population in terms of age structure.

Figure 4 - Age distribution of the population (2023) Source: OFS

Figure 5 - Age distribution of the sample (2023) Source: SHP

This discrepancy can be partly explained by design limitations of the Swiss Household Panel, where individuals under the age of 14 are not eligible to participate directly by answering the questions by themselves in the survey.⁹ As a result, the youngest age group is systematically underrepresented compared to national demographic data. Furthermore, this pattern is consistent with well-documented selection mechanisms identified in SHP methodological research. Previous studies have shown that younger respondents tend to drop out or be underrepresented over time in the SHP, while older individuals are more likely to remain in the panel, leading to an overrepresentation of older age groups in later waves. These structural and behavioral factors jointly contribute to the observed misalignment between the sample and population age distributions (Lipps, 2007). Given this observation, I decided to take away from the study this age category.

⁹ Swiss Household Panel (SHP), even though the *individual questionnaire* is only administered from age 14 and up, children from 0 to 13 years old are still represented in the dataset.

Similar checks were performed. To assess the representativeness of our sample in terms of employment, we compared the average employment rate in the dataset (2013–2022), which stands at 81.14%, with the national average over the period 2019–2023, reported as 80.16% by Eurostat (Eurostat, 2025). A Z-test for proportions confirmed that this difference is statistically significant ($Z = 7.81$, $p < 0.001$). However, the absolute difference remains relatively small (less than 1 percentage point), suggesting that, in practical terms, the sample could be approximately representative of the Swiss population with regard to employment status.

Overall, the sample used in the final analysis can be considered representative of the Swiss population with respect to sex, as no statistically significant difference was found between the sample and national distribution. For age, the average value in the sample is 43.14 years, compared to 42.9 years in the Swiss population. A Z-test on means indicated no significant difference with respect to the age average. Nevertheless, I acknowledge a difference in the distribution of the age categories that is present in all the years I tested (2013, 2018 and 2023), and this is a well-known issue of the representativeness of the SHP as highlighted by the literature.

With regard to employment status, the sample shows an employment rate of 81.14% (average over 2013–2022), compared to the national average of 80.16% over 2019–2023, as reported by Eurostat. A Z-test for proportions confirmed that this difference is statistically significant ($Z = 7.81$, $p < 0.001$) due to the large sample size ($n = 100,942$). However, the absolute difference is less than 1 percentage point, suggesting limited practical implications. Nonetheless, the sample should not be considered fully representative across all dimensions. These limitations are acknowledged, and the interpretation of the results is made with appropriate caution.

While these tests suggest a reasonable degree of representativeness along some dimensions, my empirical analysis required the use of a more restricted analysis sample. Initial estimations showed that the number of observations varied substantially across models because of differing missing data patterns, exclusion of certain health categories, and the requirements imposed by instrumental variable estimations. To ensure comparability and to avoid biases introduced by sample variation, I therefore defined a single consistent analysis

sample that was applied across all models in Part I of the thesis. This restricted sample includes only individuals observed between 2013 and 2021 with complete information on health outcomes, renovation variables, instruments, and covariates.

The final analysis sample for Part I comprises 2,628 person-year observations from 1,146 unique individuals. On average, each individual contributes 2.3 years of data to the panel. This lower panel length relative to the potential nine years (2013–2021) reflects the strict requirements of the restricted sample and the unbalanced nature of the SHP, where not all individuals are observed in every wave. Although the restrictions reduce the sample size, they ensure that all models are estimated on the exact same set of individuals and observations, thereby improving internal consistency and comparability across empirical specifications.

4.2. Variables

This section outlines the variables used in the analysis, grouped into three categories : Health indicators (dependent variables), Renovation indicators (main explanatory variables) and Control variables (covariates used to address potential confounding factors).

A key challenge encountered during the thesis was the limited availability of certain variables. For instance, *lung_illness_dummy*, is only available from 2021 onward and not in earlier years. Conversely, renovation variables related to windows are available up to 2021, but not beyond. To address these limitations, a separate sub-analysis was conducted.

4.2.1. Health Indicators

Health outcomes are measured using several self-reported indicators available in the Swiss Household Panel. The principal indicator is self-rated health (*health_status_inv*), based on a five-point ordinal scale ranging from "not well at all", "Not very well", "so, so(average)", "well" to "very well." The scale was inverted from the original scale for an easier interpretability of the results.

In addition to that, the dataset includes a binary variable¹⁰ indicating whether the respondent reports suffering from a chronic or long-term illness. A more detailed health condition is captured through a binary variable measuring the presence of lung disease¹¹. Together, these health indicators provide a comprehensive picture of individual health status and enable the analysis of both subjective and medically relevant dimensions of health, potentially influenced by housing conditions.

4.2.2. Renovation Indicators

To capture the impact of housing improvements on health outcomes, renovation indicators were constructed based on available information in the dataset. These indicators identify whether renovations were undertaken, including general energy-efficient renovations of the

¹⁰ *chronic_illness_dummy*

¹¹ *lung_illness_dummy*

habitations, like the renovations of windows. Additionally, a broader indicator (hh14) captures whether any form of renovation took place, regardless of type.

To analyze the impact of renovations on respiratory illnesses (more specifically, lung illness), and in the absence of a specific renovation variable suitable for this analysis, I constructed a new binary indicator named `renovation_applied`.

This variable was derived from the original `condition_accomodation` variable, which classifies housing conditions into three categories:

- (1) in bad condition,
- (2) in good condition but not recently renovated, and
- (3) new¹² or recently renovated.

The issue here is that, in order to recode this variable¹³ I retained only the extreme categories — (1) *in bad condition* and (3) *new or recently renovated*, as the focus is on assessing the effect of actual renovations. “*In good condition but not recently renovated*”¹⁴ was not retained, as we are focusing only on households that were renovated.

In bad condition was coded as 0 (as for this category there is no renovation at all), for the category *new or recently renovated*, I coded it as 1, as the renovation was applied.

One potential issue was observed : this recording takes into account people that moved to a new apartment too (which is not the main topic of our interest). Therefore, to isolate only the renovation, I restricted my database to only people that did not move out of residence before 2013, by employing the variable `year_moved_residence`, even before applying any modification to hh14. This makes that our study only focuses on the people that stayed in their apartment and that did not move during our study (people that stayed in their dwelling for 10 years or more). Therefore, this third category doesn't include people in a new

¹² By new, we understand an apartment of less than 10 years old.

¹³ This variable was originally hh14, then renamed after taking away the missing values to `condition_accomodation` and finally transformed to a dummy : `renovation_applied` in order to capture renovations.

¹⁴ Category 2 was taken away, as it is not the topic of our study.

apartment as we restricted everything beforehand to people that stayed in the same apartment or house for 10 years or more.

The rationale is that if individuals did not move from their dwelling, the housing unit cannot be considered new — thus, any improvement in housing condition is more likely attributable to a renovation rather than a change in residence. This restriction enhances the reliability of the `renovation_applied` variable as a proxy for capturing the causal effect of renovations on respiratory health outcomes.

In the context of Swiss housing statistics, a new dwelling is one that has been added to the housing stock in recent years—typically registered with the Federal Register of Buildings and Dwellings (RBD) upon completion. The Federal Statistical Office (FSO) notes that each year approximately 45,000 new dwellings are constructed in Switzerland.

These dwellings are often newly built rather than renovated. For the purposes of this study, distinguishing between a genuinely renovated dwelling and a newly constructed dwelling is critical. If a household has moved into a newly built residence during the study period, improvements in health outcomes could stem from the higher quality and fresh structure of the new building—not from the act of renovating existing windows.

To avoid this confounding effect—where the benefits of improved housing conditions are conflated with the effect of renovations—I restrict the sample to individuals who have not moved and have stayed in the same dwelling for at least ten years¹⁵. This ensures that the observed health impacts can be attributed to within-dwelling renovations rather than being clouded by new dwelling effects.

4.2.3. Control Variables

In all regression models, I include three control variables: age, sex, and yearly household income. Age and sex are standard demographic controls that capture basic health-related heterogeneity across individuals. Age is particularly important, as health outcomes

¹⁵ I adopt the definition that dwellings less than ten years old are treated as “new”, while those ten years or older are considered “old”.

vulnerability to respiratory or allergic conditions vary significantly across the life cycle.

Sex differences are also relevant, given documented disparities in health reporting and exposure sensitivity. Sex was included as a control variable in this study due to its well-established influence on health outcomes, for example for asthma pathophysiology and symptom expression. Clinical evidence shows that asthma prevalence and severity vary significantly between males and females across the life course. While asthma is more common in boys during childhood, its prevalence shifts after puberty, with females experiencing more frequent and severe symptoms. These differences are believed to be influenced by sex hormones—particularly estrogen and progesterone—which may enhance airway inflammation, whereas testosterone appears to have a protective anti-inflammatory effect. Hormonal fluctuations during menstruation, pregnancy, and menopause can further modulate asthma symptoms in women, contributing to greater variability and potentially poorer health outcomes. By controlling for sex, this study aims to account for these biological differences and isolate the specific effects of housing and environmental conditions on respiratory health outcomes (Fuseini & Newcomb, 2017).

Sexual dimorphism plays a significant role in other respiratory diseases such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and lung cancer, influencing not only disease susceptibility but also its severity, clinical presentation, and response to treatment. Although estrogen and testosterone are recognized as important modulators of disease progression, the exact mechanisms through which they affect lung pathophysiology remain insufficiently understood. Emerging evidence also points to genetic factors, such as dosage compensation and escape from X-chromosome inactivation (XCI), which may lead to imbalances in key regulatory genes linked to inflammation and fibrosis—core features of many lung conditions. These biological differences highlight the need to control for sex in studies investigating respiratory health, as it allows for a more accurate assessment of environmental and housing-related impacts. Moreover, considering sex as a variable can contribute to the development of more personalized and effective interventions for both males and females (Reddy & Oliver, 2023).

Yearly household income is included to account for the role of socioeconomic status, which can influence both the likelihood of undertaking renovations and baseline health outcomes.

Income influences health through multiple interconnected pathways, as highlighted by Marmot (2002). Beyond enabling access to basic material needs such as nutritious food, safe housing, and healthcare, income also shapes social status and psychosocial well-being. Individuals with higher income often experience greater autonomy, control over life circumstances, and reduced chronic stress—all of which are associated with better physical and mental health outcomes. Conversely, lower income is frequently linked to increased exposure to health risks and limited access to protective resources.

By controlling for income, the aim is to reduce potential bias stemming from differences in financial capacity to afford energy renovations or access healthcare. These variables help ensure that the estimated impact of insulation renovations on health is not confounded by basic demographic or economic characteristics.

Given the potential impact of COVID-19 on the prevalence of lung illnesses among individuals in the sample, I included the variable `cc01` — which captures whether a person had a COVID-19 infection — as a control in the analysis (Cleveland Clinic, n.d.).

4.2.4. Age restriction in the panel analysis

In Switzerland, the majority of young people enter the labor market through the vocational training system, beginning an apprenticeship at the age of 16–17 years old (Swissinfo, 2018).

Apprenticeships generally last four years, which implies that the first full-time salaried employment typically begins at around 20–21 years of age. Moreover, younger individuals are underrepresented in the Swiss Household Panel compared to the general population, which further reduces the reliability of estimates for this age group (Lipps, 2007).

Because personal incomes for minors are structurally zero and household income is not comparable across life-cycle stages, I restrict the estimation sample to individuals aged 20 and above in all models where income enters as a covariate. This restriction ensures that the analysis focuses on the population with meaningful labor income and avoids spurious variation. A restriction to people that stayed in their dwellings for 10 years or more, has been also performed in order to fully capture the impact of the renovations.

4.3. Descriptive Statistics and Preliminary Trends

The statistics on this chapter provide a useful overview of the dataset and ensure that the econometric results in the next section are built on a well-understood empirical foundation. Table 2 provides summary statistics for the key variables used in the analysis. Other variables have been included in the Table 1 of the Appendix. The dataset includes over 155'000 person-year observations, with an average respondent age of 43 years and a balanced gender distribution (51.3% female).

Table 2: Summary Statistics of Key Variables

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.	Observations	Comment
Age (years)	43.14	23.09	0	105	155'155	
Female (=1 if yes)	0.513	0.4998	0	1	155'296	
Yearly net household income (CHF)	125'735	82935	20'000	2'264'430	135'486	
Chronic illness (=1 if yes)	0.3534	0.4780	0	1	153'352	64'805 persons have a chronic illness
Lung Illness (=1 if yes)	0.0529	0.2239	0	1	26'120	769 persons have a lung illness
Insulation renovation of doors and windows (=1 if yes)	0.1903	0.3925	0	1	22'621	4305 observations

The average yearly household income is CHF 125,735. Regarding health status, approximately 22% of individuals report having a chronic illness, while 1,064 and 585 people report suffering from allergies and asthma, respectively. Insulation renovations of windows were reported in 4,305 person-year observations, representing 2.77% of the full sample. However, these observations correspond to only 887 unique individuals, indicating that some respondents reported renovations in multiple years. This aligns with the longitudinal nature of the data and may reflect repeated or multi-year renovation activities.

4.3.1. Evolution of Self-reported Health over Time

In terms of health outcomes, two important patterns emerge over time. As shown in Figure 6, average self-reported health status showed a downward trend from 2013 to 2020, followed by a notable spike in 2020.

This inflection point corresponds to the COVID-19 pandemic, which represents a major external shock that substantially affected both physical and mental health in Switzerland,

thereby influencing survey responses. This issue is taken into account when running the different models.

Figure 6 — Evolution of the self reported Health Status of Swiss Population

Note : The shaded grey area around the line illustrates the 95% confidence intervals, indicating the statistical uncertainty around each yearly estimate. Data Source : Swiss Household Panel.

4.3.2. Evolution of Chronic Illnesses over Time

Regarding chronic illnesses, the average share of individuals reporting chronic illness has steadily increased between 2013 and 2020, before experiencing a slight decline between 2020-2021. One would expect to find an increase of chronic illness after COVID-19, due to long covid or other complications appearing after that event, surprisingly we observe the opposite phenomenon : a slight decrease.

Furthermore, there was already a steady increase of chronic illness during the pre-covid period, pointing out that the increase of chronic illnesses is maybe due to other variables unrelated to COVID-19. Knowing this, I can conduct this analysis without excluding post-COVID-19 periods when including chronic illnesses.

Based on the data from the sample, the number of individuals reporting a lung illness has shown a slight increase in recent years, when controlling for people that died during COVID (see Figure 7).

Figure 7 — Evolution of chronic and lung illness prevalence from 2013 to 2023.

Note : Lung illness values (available only from 2021 to 2023) were scaled by a factor of 50 to enhance comparability with chronic illness data. Data source : constructed from the SHP.

The increase in chronic illness over time may also reflect underlying structural health trends. For instance, the prevalence of asthma has risen from 5.1% in 2017 to 6.0% in 2022, according to data from the Swiss Confederation. Similarly, other chronic illnesses such as type 2 diabetes are increasing, though at a slower pace: Escobar et al. (2015), writing in the *Swiss Medical Review*, reported a 1.5 percentage point increase in the prevalence of type 2 diabetes between 1990 and 2015. Allergies have also surged significantly in Switzerland. Pollen allergy alone rose from 1% of the population in 1921 to 20% by 2021 (Swiss Tropical and Public Health Institute, 2021). These trends are driven by several factors, including climate change, urban pollution, and broader environmental changes.

In Switzerland, respiratory illnesses represent a significant public health concern. In 2022, 6.8% of the Swiss population suffered from a chronic respiratory disease. Specifically, 5.4% of the population had received a medical diagnosis for asthma, while 2.0% were diagnosed with chronic bronchitis, symptomatic COPD (chronic obstructive pulmonary disease), or emphysema. Asthma is more prevalent among women (6.1%) than men (4.7%). In contrast, chronic bronchitis, COPD, and emphysema affect both sexes equally and become more common with age. Notably, these diseases also vary significantly with education level: individuals without post-compulsory education are more affected (5.1%) than those with an upper secondary diploma (2.6%) or a tertiary education degree (1.1%). As shown in the following image (Figure 8) from the Swiss Health Observatory (Obsan), the prevalence of respiratory illnesses is higher in the Romandy (French-speaking) region of Switzerland, while it is notably lower in the German-speaking cantons (Federal Office of Public Health, 2025).

Figure 8 – Prevalence of Chronic Respiratory Diseases in Switzerland (2022)

Source: Obsan 2025 – Swiss Health Observatory

Note: This map illustrates the proportion of the population in each Swiss canton diagnosed with a respiratory disease in 2022. The darker the shade of blue, the higher the percentage, ranging from 4.6% to 9.3%. White areas represent cantons where no extended sample was available for analysis. Data source: ©Obsan 2025.

Figure 9 – Prevalence of Lung Illness in Switzerland by Canton (2022)

Note : This map displays the percentage of individuals reporting a lung illness in each Swiss canton based on data from the Swiss Household Panel (SHP) for the year 2022. The color scale reflects the proportion of affected individuals, with darker shades indicating higher prevalence. Cantons with missing or insufficient data are shown in grey. Data source : constructed from the SHP.

Figure 9 illustrates the spatial distribution of lung illness prevalence across Swiss cantons in 2022, based on data from the Swiss Household Panel. The map reveals notable regional disparities: cantons located in the Romandy region (French-speaking Switzerland), particularly in the western and southwestern parts of the country, appear to exhibit a higher proportion of individuals reporting lung illness, with several cantons falling within the darkest categories of prevalence ($\geq 6.87\%$).

In contrast, many central and eastern cantons show lower reported rates, while a few regions lack sufficient data. This regional pattern may reflect underlying differences in environmental conditions, housing quality, pollution levels, or sociodemographic characteristics, warranting further investigation.

4.3.3. Descriptive Statistics of the Windows Insulation

In what concerns insulation renovations, the yearly distribution shows clear temporal fluctuations, likely shaped by both policy dynamics and external shocks. As illustrated in Figure 10, the highest number of reported window renovations occurred in 2013, with over 700 renovations. This was followed by a gradual decline, with renovation counts stabilizing between 2016 and 2019 at around 400 per year.

A striking drop is observed in 2020, coinciding with the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, which likely disrupted renovation plans due to lockdown measures, economic uncertainty, and construction delays. In 2021, renovation activity rebounded to over 500 observations, indicating a partial recovery. These patterns highlight the non-random nature of renovation timing, underscoring the need to control for year effects and external shocks in the analysis. Moreover, they support the relevance of using an instrumental variable approach to isolate the causal impact of insulation renovations on health outcomes.

Figure 10 - Number of Renovations per Year (2013-2021)

Data Source : Swiss Household Panel

The decline in renovations over the study period may be explained by the fact that a very large wave of renovations likely occurred shortly after the introduction of *Le Programme*

Bâtiments in 2010, which provided financial incentives for energy-efficient renovations. The highest spike was probably in 2010–2011, but this lies outside the timeline of the present analysis. As the years progressed, the number of annual renovations decreased, possibly because many eligible buildings had already been upgraded. In 2020, renovations almost stopped due to COVID-19 restrictions on economic activities, followed by a sharp rebound in 2021 as projects resumed.

4.3.4. Evolution of Health over Time by Housing Conditions

Acknowledging the descriptive statistics, I proceeded to analyze the evolution of reported health over time for two groups: individuals living in poor housing conditions and those residing in good or recently renovated dwellings.

Figure 11 presents this comparison by plotting the average reversed self-reported health score from the early 2000s to 2023. To construct this figure in order to visualize how average self-reported health evolved by housing condition, I produced a purely descriptive plot using the Swiss Household Panel microdata. The binary variable `condition_good_dummy` identifies whether the respondent lived in a recently renovated dwelling or new (coded 1) or in a poorly maintained one (coded 0).

Figure 11. — Average self-reported health over time by housing condition (2000–2023).

Note : This figure shows the evolution of average health scores on a 1-to-5 scale (1 = worst, 5 = best) based on housing condition.

The health score ranges from 1 (very poor health) to 5 (very good health). I collapsed the data to compute yearly averages for each group, which allowed me to plot the trends over time. The graph reveals a consistent gap between the two groups, with individuals in better housing reporting better average health. While this is an observational result, one hypothetical explanation for the gap could be that individuals living in poor housing conditions are more exposed to factors such as dampness, cold, or poor air quality, which may negatively affect

their health. In contrast, renovated or well-maintained dwellings may offer better protection and comfort, thereby improving perceived health outcomes. However, this interpretation remains hypothetical and does not establish a definitive causal link.

Interestingly, the health of the poorly housed group is not only lower on average, but also displays greater fluctuations, which may reflect their heightened vulnerability to external shocks such as economic downturns or health crises. The red dashed line, representing individuals in good or renovated housing, remains relatively flat with a slight decrease over time. This pattern is likely due to a ceiling effect, where many individuals report high health scores (4–5), limiting visible improvement.

Although this graph does not establish causality, it serves as a compelling visual motivation for further investigation. The persistence of the health gap over time raises critical questions: to what extent does housing quality impact health? Could renovations offer a pathway to reduce health inequalities? These descriptive patterns awaken our curiosity and underscore the need for a more rigorous empirical approach. The subsequent sections of this study aim to address these questions using panel data methods and an instrumental variable strategy, allowing us to move beyond correlation and assess the potential causal effects of housing renovation on health.

5. Methodology

5.1. Endogeneity and Subsidies as Instrumental Variable

Estimating the causal impact of insulation renovations on health outcomes presents significant methodological challenges, primarily due to potential endogeneity in the renovation decision. It is renovation that is expected to influence health—but could it be that healthier individuals, which are reported to be statistically healthier, are simply more likely to renovate?

To address these endogeneity concerns, this study employs an Instrumental Variable (IV) approach, leveraging cantonal-level subsidies for insulation renovations provided under the *Programme Bâtiments, from 2013 to 2021*, while controlling for sex, age and income. This spatial and temporal variation forms the basis for the instrumental variable used in the analysis, under the assumption that cantonal differences in subsidy generosity influence renovation decisions but are exogenous to individual household health outcomes. These subsidies, varying across cantons and over time, aim to promote energy efficiency in the residential sector by reducing the financial burden of insulation improvements for households. Utilizing this exogenous policy variation allows, in principle, for the identification of a causal relationship between insulation renovations and health outcomes.

For an instrument to be valid, it must satisfy two key conditions: relevance and exogeneity.

1. **Relevance:** The instrument must be strongly correlated with the endogenous regressor—in this case, the decision to undertake insulation renovations. The cantonal subsidies fulfill this criterion, as higher subsidy levels lower the effective cost of renovations, thereby increasing the likelihood of households initiating such projects.

$$\text{Cov}(Z, X) \neq 0$$

2. **Exclusion Restriction:** The instrument must not be correlated with the error term in the health outcome equation; that is, it should not directly affect health outcomes except through its impact on renovation decisions.

$$\text{Cov}(Z, \varepsilon) = 0$$

3. Independence: The instrument should be uncorrelated with the error term in the outcome equation. This means that the instrument should not be influenced by any omitted variables or factors that are correlated with the outcome variable. Essentially, the instrument should be as good as randomly assigned to the units in the sample.

The use of cantonal subsidies for insulation renovations as an instrumental variable satisfies the three required conditions for instrument validity:

1. Relevance: Cantonal subsidies directly reduce the cost of insulation renovations. If a household knows it will receive financial support, it's more likely to renovate. This means there's a statistical and economic relationship between the level of subsidy and the probability of renovation. This can be checked with a first-stage regression. According to Stock and Yogo (2010), an F-statistic of 10 or greater in the first-stage regression is a commonly cited rule of thumb for identifying strong instruments (Stock & Yogo, 2010). However, recent methodological advances highlight the limitations of this heuristic. In particular, Lee, McCrary, Moreira, and Porter demonstrate that in designs with heteroskedasticity, clustered errors, or multiple instruments, first-stage F-statistics may need to exceed 100 to ensure valid structural inference and proper size control in hypothesis tests. In this thesis, as I only have one instrument, I will use as a reference an F-statistic of 10 or greater (Leet et al, 2022), and adapt the minimum level required by using the reference tables of Stock and Yogo for a more accurate F-statistic in function of the type of model.
2. Exogeneity: The subsidy amount is determined by canton-level policies (based on energy goals, not individual health). Households don't receive subsidies because of their health, and subsidies do not directly affect health (e.g., subsidies don't include money for healthcare or medicines). As long as individual-level variables (like income, age, etc.) are controlled, the subsidy is exogenous.
3. Independence: There is no theoretical basis or empirical evidence suggesting that any household would be less likely to renovate their home as subsidies increase. Higher subsidies can only make people more likely to renovate or have no effect. It's not

reasonable to expect anyone to renovate less when the subsidy increases. Therefore, this condition holds.

During the redaction of this research, I plotted this instrumental variable, to see if there are some patterns across cantons. Figure 12 illustrates the distribution of cantonal subsidies for renovations in Switzerland for the years 2013, 2016, 2017, and 2021, based on data from *Le Programme Bâtiments*.

Figure 12.—Swiss Cantonal Subsidy Levels for Energy Renovations (2013, 2016, 2017, 2021).

Note : This figure illustrates the variation in cantonal subsidy levels across Switzerland for the years 2013, 2016, 2017, and 2021, based on data from *Le Programme Bâtiments*. Cantons are categorized into three levels: low (light blue), medium (medium blue), and high (dark blue) subsidy levels.

The total amount of subsidies allocated by the Confederation is already adjusted to account for the size of the canton (through the number of buildings or the population). Therefore, it is not necessary to normalize by population, as the observed variation already reflects

differences in policy intensity between cantons, which is precisely the instrumental variation being sought. To facilitate comparisons across cantons and over time, the original financial aid amounts were normalized on a scale from 0 to 1, and then classified into three categories: low, medium, and high subsidy levels. It is apparent that cantons such as Vaud (VD), Bern (BE), Zurich (ZH), and St. Gallen (SG) consistently fall into the high subsidy category. This pattern can be explained largely by the population size of these cantons. According to the OFS cited in *swissinfo.ch*, Switzerland's population is unevenly distributed, with the most populous cantons concentrated in urban and economically active regions.

These areas also attract high numbers of commuters and are home to dense residential zones, leading to a greater demand for renovation subsidies. Consequently, more financial resources are allocated to these cantons. This demographic-driven allocation supports the validity of cantonal subsidies as an instrumental variable in this study: the variation is policy-driven and exogenous to individual household health conditions, thereby reinforcing the strength of the instrument in identifying the causal impact of renovations on health (Swissinfo.ch, 2007).

5.2. Isolating the impact of COVID-19

To better isolate the impact of renovation on respiratory health outcomes, I control for potential confounding effects related to the Covid-19 pandemic. I initially considered including an interaction term between Covid-19 infection (cc01) and the "Covid-19 risk group" indicator, which captures whether the individual was identified as particularly vulnerable to complications from the virus (e.g., due to asthma, cancer, or other chronic conditions). The rationale was to test whether Covid-19 infections had a more severe impact on individuals in at-risk categories. However, I ultimately excluded this interaction from the main specification.

The reason is that the risk group variable is partially defined by pre-existing respiratory conditions, which overlap with the outcomes I aim to explain (such as lung illness). Including it would therefore risk overcontrolling, absorbing part of the effect that insulation renovations might have on respiratory health. For this reason, I chose to exclude the risk group indicator and its interaction with Covid-19 infection from the final model, in order to preserve the

integrity of the causal pathway. Furthermore, I will just control for COVID-19 infection, as it is well known by literature that this infection can have an impact on lung illness prevalence. In chapter 6, I am going to evaluate the strength of the instrument to know if the results of our method could be considered as viable.

5.3. Identification strategy for the impact of renovations on general health

To estimate the effect of housing renovation on individual health outcomes, I begin by employing a series of progressively robust econometric models, each designed to address specific sources of bias.

Model (1) : Linear Fixed-Effects model

In this model the purpose is to estimate the effect of window renovation on self-reported health (treated as a continuous outcome). The main specification, presented in Equation (1), regresses health outcomes on renovation status, log household income, age, and year fixed effects, with 2021 serving as the reference year. The sex variable is excluded because it is time-invariant at the individual level and therefore absorbed by the fixed effects. In contrast, income is retained as a control because it exhibits substantial variation over time and can influence both health and renovation decisions.

Household income in Switzerland exhibits meaningful year-to-year variation, even when excluding promotions or major career changes. According to the Swiss Federal Statistical Office (BFS), nominal wages in Switzerland grow on average by about 1.5% per year, even excluding promotions or job changes. For a median wage of CHF 74,000, this corresponds to an increase of roughly CHF 1,100 per year, or over CHF 11,000 across a decade. This illustrates that household income is not time-invariant, and thus justifies its inclusion as a time-varying control in fixed-effects models. Including it as a control in the fixed-effects model is therefore justified, as it captures genuine economic dynamics that could influence both health outcomes and renovation decisions.

Eq (1)

$$Health_{it}^{Inv} = \beta_1 \cdot Renovation_{it} + \beta_2 \cdot \log(Income_{it}) + \beta_3 \cdot Age_{it} + \delta_t + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where :

$Health_{it}^{Inv}$: Inverted self-reported health score for individual i at time t . This continuous variable ranges from 1 (very good health) to 5 (very bad health), where a higher value indicates worse perceived health. The variable is inverted for interpretability: lower values reflect better health.

$Renovation_{it}$: Binary or continuous indicator of whether the household i underwent a renovation at time t . It captures the exposure to energy-efficient housing improvements aimed at reducing indoor pollution and improving living conditions.

$\log(Income_{it})$: Natural logarithm of household income for individual i at time t . This transformation reduces the influence of outliers and captures the diminishing marginal effect of income on health.

Age_{it} : Age of individual i at time t . This variable controls for natural changes in health associated with aging.

δ_t : year fixed effects

α_i : Individual fixed effects accounting for time-invariant unobserved heterogeneity, such as genetic predispositions, personality traits, or baseline health.

ε_{it} : Idiosyncratic error term

While the fixed effects linear regression model provides a useful first step in estimating the relationship between window renovation and self-reported health, it does not account for potential endogeneity of the renovation variable. Although individual fixed effects control for time-invariant unobserved heterogeneity, the model still relies on the assumption of strict exogeneity—namely, that renovation decisions are uncorrelated with the time-varying error term.

This assumption may be violated if, for example, individuals in better health are more likely to invest in renovations (reverse causality), or if unobserved time-varying factors (such as changes in household wealth or awareness of renovation subsidies) influence both renovation and health outcomes. As a result, the estimated effect of renovation on health in this model may be biased. To address this limitation and strengthen causal inference, I implement instrumental variable techniques and a control function approach in subsequent models.

Model (2) : Ordered logit model (pooled)

Although the self-reported health variable ranges from 1 to 5 and can be treated as quasi-continuous in some contexts, it is fundamentally an ordinal variable. The use of a fixed effects linear regression model assumes continuity for simplicity and interpretability. However, to ensure the robustness of the results, an ordered logit model is also estimated, which explicitly accounts for the ordinal nature of the dependent variable. This allows for a comparison of model outcomes and helps verify whether the linearity assumption materially affects the conclusions.

Here $Health_{it}^{Inv}$ represents the latent continuous health index. The latent continuous equation in an ordered logit model represents an unobserved health score that determines how individuals classify their health into ordinal categories. The ordered health responses we observe (from 1 to 5) are determined by where this unobserved score falls relative to estimated threshold values. Unlike in the fixed-effects model, sex is included here because it is time-invariant and not absorbed in the pooled specification.

Eq(2)

$$Health_{it}^{Inv} = \beta_1 \cdot Renovation_{it} + \beta_2 \cdot \log(Income_{it}) + \beta_3 \cdot Age_{it} + \beta_4 \cdot Sex_{it} + \delta_t + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where :

$Health_{it}^{Inv}$: Latent continuous health score for individual i at time t

$Renovation_{it}$: Binary variable equal to 1 if the respondent's household underwent window renovation, 0 otherwise.

$\log(Income_{it})$: Log-transformed household income, accounting for non-linear effects of income on health. It serves as a control variable for socioeconomic status.

Age_{it} : Age of the respondent at time t , included as a demographic control reflecting age-related health trends.

Sex_{it} : Dummy variable equal to 1 for female respondents, 0 otherwise. This controls for gender-based differences in reported health.

δ_t : Year fixed effects capturing time-specific unobserved shocks (e.g., policy changes, pandemics) that affect all individuals in a given year.

ε_{it} : Idiosyncratic error term, capturing unobserved influences on latent health at the individual-year level.

This is the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the ordered logit model (Equation 3), where τ_j represent the estimated threshold parameters between outcome categories, and $X_{it}\beta$ denotes the linear predictor composed of covariates.

Eq (3)

$$P(\text{Health}_{it} = j) = \frac{e^{\tau_j - X_{it}\beta}}{1 + e^{\tau_j - X_{it}\beta}}, \quad j = 1, \dots, 5$$

Where :

Health_{it} : ordinal value for health (1 to 5)

X_{it} : weighted sum of covariates (renovation, log income, age, ...)

τ_j : threshold parameters between levels of health

In this model I use a pooled specification rather than panel data techniques to avoid complications related to fixed effects in nonlinear models. The model includes key covariates such as the renovation indicator, log-transformed income, age, sex, and year dummies to control for time-specific effects. This approach helps verify whether the relationship between renovation and health is consistent when using a more appropriate statistical framework for ordinal outcomes. However, it does not address unobserved individual heterogeneity or endogeneity, which are dealt with in later models.

More specifically, this model is estimated as a pooled ordered logit with year dummies but without individual random effects, since the purpose is to check robustness of the linearity assumption rather than to exploit the panel structure. Unobserved heterogeneity is instead controlled in the fixed-effects model (Model 1). In other words, Model (2) serves as a robustness check to verify whether the results from the fixed-effects linear regression (Model 1) are sensitive to the treatment of self-reported health as a continuous variable. Unlike the linear specification, the ordered logit explicitly accounts for the ordinal nature of the health scale, estimating thresholds between categories rather than assuming equal spacing. The consistency of results across Models (1) and (2) provides reassurance that the conclusions are

not driven by functional form assumptions. Since the objective is robustness rather than causal identification, the model is estimated as a pooled ordered logit with year dummies but without individual random effects.

Model (3) : Control Function – Binary Probit-Probit

To address the potential endogeneity of the renovation variable in estimating its impact on self-reported health, this study adopts a control function approach—an instrumental variable (IV) method specifically adapted for nonlinear models such as probit regressions.

In the first stage, a probit model is estimated to predict the likelihood of undergoing a renovation. The binary renovation indicator is regressed on the cantonal subsidy amount (used as an instrument), along with a set of control variables including age, sex, and log-transformed household income. The residuals from this regression are then extracted to capture unobserved factors that may be jointly correlated with both renovation decisions and health outcomes. In this model, both the endogenous regressor (renovation) and the outcome (binary health) are binary variables. Following Rivers & Vuong (Rivers & Vuong, 1988), I therefore estimate the first stage as a probit, which ensures that predicted values remain in $[0,1]$ and yields generalized residuals suitable for inclusion in the second-stage probit. When both stages are binary, a linear first stage (LPM) can be poorly behaved: it may predict probabilities outside $[0,1]$ and produce residuals with the wrong distributional properties for the second-stage probit. Wooldridge supports this approach for binary choice models (Wooldridge, 2010).

Using a probit/logit first stage ensures that the residual $(y - \hat{p})$ has the right statistical form to correct endogeneity in the second-stage probit. Following Blundell & Powell (2003) and Wooldridge (2010), the first-stage residual is defined as the difference between the observed renovation outcome and its predicted probability $Residual_{it} = Renovation_{it} - \hat{p}_{it}$. This generalized residual captures unobserved factors affecting the renovation decision and, when included in the second-stage regression, corrects for potential endogeneity.

In the second stage, a probit model is estimated where the dependent variable is a binary indicator for good self-reported health (*good_health_dummy*), coded as 1 if respondents reported their health as good or very good, and 0 otherwise. The explanatory variables include the renovation dummy, the first-stage residuals, and the same set of covariates as in the first stage.

This approach follows the control function framework developed by Blundell and Powell, which extends the application of IV methods to nonlinear models by including the first-stage residuals to correct for endogenous selection. In this specification, the residual term is statistically insignificant ($p = 0.382$), suggesting that endogeneity may not be a significant concern in this context. Nonetheless, incorporating the control function reinforces the robustness of the causal interpretation by addressing potential omitted variable bias while maintaining the consistency of the probit estimator (Blundell and Powell, 2003).

This model provides an important intermediate step in the identification strategy, particularly by introducing instrumental variable logic in a nonlinear setting. It also serves as a useful complement to the subsequent ordered probit model with control function (Model 4), which extends this strategy to account for the full ordinal nature of the health outcome.

Eq(4)

FIRST STAGE :

$$\Pr (Renovation_{it} = 1) = \Phi (u_{it} + \pi_0 + \pi_1 \cdot SubsidyAmount_{ct} + \pi_2 \cdot Age_{it} + \pi_3 \cdot Sex_{it} + \pi_4 \cdot \log (Income_{it}))$$

$$Residual_{it} = Renovation_{it} - \widehat{p}_{it}$$

This residual captures unobserved variation in the renovation decision that is not explained by the instrument and controls. Including this residual in the second-stage model helps correct for endogeneity of the renovation variable.

Where :

$Renovation_{it}$: Binary variable equal to 1 if the respondent's household underwent window renovation, 0 otherwise.

$SubsidyAmount_{ct}$: Cantonal subsidy amount in canton c and year t, used as an instrument for renovation.

Age_{it} : Age of the respondent at time t, included as a demographic control reflecting age-related health trends.

Sex_{it} : Dummy variable equal to 1 for female respondents, 0 otherwise. This controls for gender-based differences in reported health.

$\log (Income_{it})$: Log-transformed household income, accounting for non-linear effects of income on health. It serves as a control variable for socioeconomic status.

\widehat{p}_{it} : Predicted probability of renovation from the first-stage probit.

$Residual_{it}$: Difference between observed renovation and its predicted probability; serves as the control function to adjust for endogeneity in the second stage.

u_{it} : Error term in the first-stage probit, assumed to follow a standard normal distribution.

Eq(5)

SECOND STAGE :

$$P(GoodHealth_{it} = 1) = \Phi(e_i + \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot Renovation_{it} + \beta_2 \cdot Age_{it} + \beta_3 \cdot Sex_{it} + \beta_4 \cdot \log(Income_{it}) + \beta_5 \cdot Residual_{it})$$

Where :

$GoodHealth_{it}$: Binary dependent variable equal to 1 if respondent i at time t reports “good” or “very good” health, 0 otherwise.

$Renovation_{it}$: same as above.

Age_{it} : same as above.

Sex_{it} : same as above.

$\log(Income_{it})$: Same as above.

e_i : Individual-specific error term, capturing unobserved heterogeneity in the health outcome that is not explained by the included covariates.

While Model (3) applies the control function approach to a binary health outcome, it simplifies the original five-category self-reported health variable into a dichotomous indicator (good vs. not good). This simplification, although convenient for estimation, involves a loss of information and may mask meaningful variation in health perceptions across individuals.

Model (4) : IV Ordered Probit with Control Function

Model (4) represents the most comprehensive specification in this study, combining an ordered probit framework with a control function approach to address both the ordinal nature of the health outcome and the potential endogeneity of the renovation variable. The motivation for implementing this model stems from two key considerations. First, self-reported health is measured on an ordinal scale with five categories, reflecting increasing levels of perceived health. Unlike linear or binary models, the ordered probit framework preserves this ranking without assuming equal distances between categories, making it a more appropriate choice for modeling subjective health evaluations. Second, the decision to renovate may be influenced by unobserved household characteristics—such as risk preferences or health awareness—that are also correlated with health outcomes. To correct for this potential endogeneity, the control function method is applied by including the residuals from a first-stage regression where renovation is instrumented using cantonal subsidy amounts.

Although renovation is binary, the first stage is estimated linearly, as the control function framework requires only a consistent reduced-form projection.

I considered whether to use a probit in the first stage since the renovation variable is binary. However, according to Wooldridge (2010) and Angrist & Pischke (2009), the standard approach in IV is to use a linear first stage, even when the endogenous regressor is binary, because OLS provides consistent fitted values for the control function. The nonlinear first stage complicates estimation without changing the asymptotics. Since my dependent variable is ordinal, I applied an ordered probit IV in the second stage, which aligns with Wooldridge's recommendation for ordinal outcomes. Therefore, my specification is consistent with econometric best practice.

Results are robust to a probit first stage. This combination allows for consistent estimation of the effect of renovations on health while fully leveraging the richness of the data.

Eq(6)

FIRST STAGE :

$$Renovation_{it} = \delta_1 \cdot SubsidyAm_{ct} + \delta_2 \cdot \log(Income_{it}) + \delta_3 \cdot (SubsidyAm_{ct} * \log(Income)_{it}) + \delta_4 \cdot Age_{it} + \delta_5 \cdot Sex_{it} + u_{it}$$

$$Residual_{it} = Renovation_{it} - \widehat{Renovation}_{it}$$

This residual captures unobserved influences on renovation decisions, which may also correlate with health.

Eq(7)

SECOND STAGE:

$$Pr(Health_{it}^{Inv} \leq j) = \Phi(\theta_j - \beta_1 \cdot Renovation_{it} - \beta_2 \cdot Residual_{it} - \beta_3 \cdot Age_{it} - \beta_4 \cdot Sex_{it} - \beta_5 \cdot \log(Income_{it}))$$

In Eq(7), θ_j represents the estimated cutpoints of the ordered probit model. These thresholds partition the latent continuous health index into the observed self-reported health categories (1 to 5). The ordered probit jointly estimates both the slope coefficients (β) and these thresholds, which allow mapping from the continuous latent health score to the discrete reported categories.

Model (4) thus serves as the most robust empirical strategy in the analysis, offering both a theoretically sound and policy-relevant assessment of how housing interventions may influence population health.

5.4. Identification strategy for the impact of renovations on respiratory health

Model (5) : IV-Probit

To assess the causal impact of housing renovations on respiratory health, I implement an instrumental variable probit (IV-Probit) model, which is specifically designed to handle binary outcome variables in the presence of endogenous regressors. In this case, the dependent variable is a binary indicator for whether the individual reports a lung illness (*lung_illness_dummy*), and the potentially endogenous regressor is the binary variable indicating whether a renovation was applied (*renovation_applied*). The renovation variable was created by following an isolation strategy : I coded the past variable with three categories *condition_accomodation* and I took away the intermediate value. Before that, I restricted the sample with people that moved the last time before 2021 and not after, so I can ensure that the dwelling is not new but just renovated.

Endogeneity may arise if unobserved household or individual characteristics—such as health awareness, risk aversion, or housing preferences—influence both the decision to renovate and the health outcome. To address this concern, I use the cantonal subsidy amount as an instrument, based on the assumption that subsidies affect the likelihood of renovation but are not directly correlated with individual health outcomes, conditional on other controls.

The first stage involves a linear regression in which the renovation dummy is regressed on the cantonal subsidy amount, its interaction with household income, and a set of exogenous covariates, including age, sex, log-transformed income, COVID-19 infection (*cc01*), and year fixed effects. This stage identifies the exogenous variation in renovation decisions driven by differences in subsidy exposure. The second stage estimates a probit model for the lung illness outcome, instrumenting the endogenous renovation variable with its predicted values from the first stage. The control variables from the first stage are included again in the second stage to ensure consistency.

This IV-Probit framework¹⁶ corrects for potential selection bias due to endogeneity and provides consistent estimates of the effect of renovation on the probability of reporting a lung illness. The use of marginal effects further facilitates interpretation by expressing the estimated coefficients as changes in probability rather than in latent utility space. This model offers a robust identification strategy and is particularly suited to binary health outcomes where both causal inference and nonlinear modeling are necessary.

Eq(8)

FIRST STAGE :

$$Renovation_{it} = \delta_1 \cdot SubsidyAm_{ct} + \delta_2 \cdot \log(Income_{it}) + \delta_3 \cdot (SubsidyAm * \log(Income))_{it} + \delta_4 Age_{it} + \delta_5 Sex_{it} + u_{it}$$

Eq(9)

SECOND STAGE :

The latent propensity to suffer from lung illness will be :

$$LungIllness_i^* = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot Renovation_i + Z_i' \beta + \varepsilon_i$$

The observed probability is :

$$P(LungIllness_i = 1) = \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot Renovation_i + Z_i' \beta)$$

In the model equations, the term $Z_i' \beta$ denotes the matrix product between a vector of exogenous explanatory variables Z_i and a corresponding vector of coefficients β .

$$Z_i = \begin{bmatrix} age_i \\ sex_i \\ \log(income_i) \\ region_i \\ year\ dummies_i \end{bmatrix}, \quad \beta = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_2 \\ \beta_3 \\ \beta_4 \\ \beta_5 \\ \beta_6 \end{bmatrix}$$

¹⁶ The IV-Probit model follows the limited-information maximum likelihood approach of Amemiya (Amemiya, 1978). In this framework, the first stage can be estimated linearly, as consistency requires only a reduced-form projection of the endogenous regressor on the instrument set. This differs from the Rivers–Vuong control function estimator (Model 3), which requires a probit first stage when both the endogenous regressor and the outcome are binary (Rivers & Vuong, 1988; Wooldridge, 2010).

In the context of this analysis, Z_i includes variables such as age, sex, log-transformed income, COVID-19 infection (cc01), year fixed effects, and the interaction between subsidy amounts and income. Including these controls helps account for observable individual characteristics that may simultaneously influence both the likelihood of undergoing a renovation and the risk of developing respiratory illness, thereby improving the accuracy and robustness of the estimated treatment effect.

Unlike the control function specifications discussed earlier, the IV-Probit model does not require the explicit computation or inclusion of a first-stage residual in the second-stage equation. This is because the IV-Probit estimator, following Amemiya (1978) and Rivers & Vuong (1988), is estimated by maximum likelihood and jointly models both the renovation equation and the health outcome equation. In this framework, the correlation between the unobserved determinants of renovation and the unobserved determinants of health is captured directly through a correlation parameter (ρ) in the likelihood function. As a result, the potential endogeneity of the renovation variable is accounted for internally, and there is no need to append a residual term to the health equation, as would be necessary in a two-step control function approach. This distinction ensures that the IV-Probit specification remains consistent and efficient while avoiding redundancy in the estimation.

6. Results

6.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics for the variables used to assess the relationship between energy-efficient renovations and self-reported health outcomes. The dataset includes 4,381 observations, which correspond to individual-level information after data cleaning and merging household- and person-level variables from the Swiss Household Panel.

The dependent variable, *health_scale_inv*, ranges from 1 to 5, with a mean value of 4.02 and a standard deviation of 0.66. This indicates that, on average, individuals report a relatively high level of health, with moderate variation across respondents.

Table 3: Summary of the descriptive statistics for the impact of renovations on health

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
<i>health_scale_inv</i>	4,381	4.0205	0.6580	1	5
<i>renovated_windows</i>	4,381	0.5286	0.4992	0	1
<i>log_income</i>	4,381	11.5974	0.5841	7.8240	14.4225
<i>age</i>	4,381	54.5156	16.2934	20	96
<i>sex_dummy</i>	4,381	0.5378	0.4986	0	1
<i>yearly_household_income</i>	4,381	128,400.9	86,774.4	2,500	1,834,910

Notes: This table reports summary statistics for the main variables used in the analysis examining the impact of renovations on health outcomes.

The main explanatory variable, *renovated_windows*, has a mean of 0.53, showing that slightly more than half of the sampled households underwent window or door renovation during the observation period. This balanced distribution provides sufficient variation to identify the potential impact of renovations on health. Among the control variables, the logarithm of income (mean = 11.60) shows relatively low dispersion (SD = 0.58), reflecting the typical income distribution in Switzerland after transformation to reduce skewness. The average age of respondents is 54.5 years, with values ranging from 20 to 96, suggesting that the sample covers a wide demographic spectrum of adults and elderly individuals. The *sex_dummy* variable indicates that 53.8% of the respondents are women, ensuring near gender balance in the sample. Finally, the variable *yearly_household_income* shows a mean of approximately CHF 128,401 per year, but with a large standard deviation (CHF 86,774). This wide dispersion highlights considerable heterogeneity in household income, consistent with the inclusion of both low- and high-income households in the dataset.

Overall, these descriptive statistics indicate a well-balanced and heterogeneous sample suitable for investigating how building renovations—particularly window and door improvements—are associated with self-reported health outcomes in Switzerland.

6.2. Results for the impact of renovations on health

Table 4 presents the results from four econometric specifications estimating the impact of window renovation on self-reported health. The dependent variable in Models 1 and 2 is the *health scale* (ranging from 1 to 5), while in Models 3 and 4 it is a dummy for *good or very good health*. Each model gradually refines the estimation strategy to address potential biases and assess the robustness of the results.

Table 4: Results for the different models

	M1	M2	M3	M4
	Linear model	Ordered logit (pooled)	Control Function	IV-Probit
Renovated windows	0.0145 (0.0199)	-0.0217 (0.0623)	5.419 (3.728)	0.0682* (0.0360)
Log income	-0.077 (0.0455)	0.2694*** (0.0559)	0.0576** (0.4669)	0.1568*** (0.0312)
Age	-0.0149** (0.0061)	-0.0168*** (0.0020)	0.0184 (0.0172)	-0.0057*** (0.0017)
Sex (female = 1)	-	-0.2206*** (0.0627)	-0.0300 (0.0988)	-0.0478*** (0.0506)
Year FE	Yes	Yes	No	No
Cut 1	-	-3.721 (0.7470)	-	-1.4822 (0.3922)
Cut 2	-	-1.762 (0.7051)	-	-0.5768 (0.3891)
Cut 3	-	0.3366 (0.7000)	-	0.2542 (0.3868)
Cut 4	-	3.5399 (0.7028)	-	2.1684 (0.3876)
<i>Model Statistics</i>				
Observations	4,381	4,381	3,810	4,381
Individuals	1,968	1,968	1,146	1,968
Pseudo R ²	0.0213	0.0174	0.0427	0.0169
F statistic	-	-	-	17.25

Notes: None of the year dummies are statistically significant. M3 outcome is a dummy variable for *good.health.dummy*. In M4, the first-stage F-statistic equals 17.25, which exceeds the Stock-Yogo (2005) critical value of 16.38, indicating a strong instrument. The IV-Probit model is estimated with robust standard errors. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

Model 1: Linear Fixed-Effects Model

Model 1 estimates a fixed-effects (within) regression controlling for unobserved individual heterogeneity over time. The coefficient of *renovated_windows* is positive (0.0145) but statistically insignificant, suggesting that, on average, window renovation is not directly associated with a measurable improvement in self-reported health when controlling for individual fixed effects. The within R^2 is relatively low (0.0058), which is common in micro-level health data, reflecting that much of the health variation is driven by time-invariant personal characteristics rather than by short-term housing changes.

Among the control variables, age has a negative and statistically significant coefficient ($-0.0149, p < 0.05$), indicating that self-reported health tends to decline with age, holding other factors constant. Income and year dummies are not statistically significant, suggesting that short-term income changes or year-specific effects do not strongly influence perceived health in this model.

Model 2: Ordered Logit (Pooled)

Model 2 re-estimates the relationship using a pooled ordered logit model, acknowledging the ordinal nature of the health scale. The results show a small negative but insignificant coefficient for *renovated_windows* (-0.0217), consistent with Model 1. However, log income is now positively and strongly significant ($p < 0.01$), with a coefficient of 0.2694, indicating that higher income levels are associated with better self-reported health. This aligns with established literature linking socioeconomic status to health outcomes.

Both age and female gender remain significant, with negative signs, confirming that health perception declines with age and that women, on average, report slightly lower health levels than men after controlling for income and other factors. The model's Pseudo R^2 is modest (0.0174), yet the results provide a consistent baseline for the subsequent models.

Model 3: Control Function Approach

Model 3 applies a control function approach, where the outcome variable is recoded as a dummy for *good health* and the residuals from the first-stage regression are included to address potential endogeneity. The coefficient on *renovated_windows* is large and positive (5.419) but statistically insignificant due to high standard errors, reflecting limited precision. This instability is likely due to the smaller sample size (3,810 observations) caused by the exclusion of one health category that

disappeared in this recoding. In fact, the outcome is a dummy variable in this part, excluding all the intermediate categories.

Nevertheless, the positive sign may suggest that, once endogeneity is controlled for, renovation could improve health outcomes, although the effect cannot be confirmed statistically. Log income remains positive and significant ($p < 0.05$), reinforcing the robustness of the income–health gradient across model specifications.

Model 4: IV-Probit Estimation

Model 4 employs an Instrumental Variable Probit (IV-Probit) estimation, using cantonal renovation subsidies as an instrument for *renovated_windows*. The coefficient (0.0682) is positive and statistically significant ($p < 0.1$), suggesting that once potential endogeneity is accounted for, window renovations have a beneficial impact on health, increasing the likelihood of reporting good or very good health. This finding supports the hypothesis that improving the thermal and air quality conditions of a dwelling can enhance perceived well-being and health.

The strength of the instrument is validated by the first-stage F-statistic of 17.25, which exceeds the Stock–Yogo (2005) critical threshold of 16.38 for weak instrument bias. This indicates that the instrument is sufficiently strong to yield reliable estimates. Moreover, the IV-Probit estimation accounts for heteroskedasticity by using robust standard errors, ensuring consistent inference.

Interpretation and Comparison Across Models

Across the four specifications, the sign of the renovation coefficient is consistently positive (except in M2, where it is close to zero), reinforcing the idea that renovations may improve health outcomes, even if statistical significance appears only after instrumenting for endogeneity. The models demonstrate that ignoring endogeneity (as in M1 and M2) might underestimate the true effect of renovations on health, likely due to selection bias — healthier or wealthier households might be more likely to renovate in the first place.

Control variables behave as expected: income is a consistent and significant predictor of better health, while age and female gender are associated with slightly worse health outcomes. None of the year dummies are significant, implying that time effects such as macroeconomic or policy shocks did not materially affect self-reported health within the study period.

6.3. Average Marginal Effects for the impact of the renovation on the health of Swiss Households

Table 5 reports the Average Marginal Effects (AMEs) derived from the instrumental variable probit model (M4), which estimates the marginal impact of energy-efficient renovations on the probability of belonging to each self-reported health category. The dependent variable, *health_scale_inv*, ranges from 1 (very poor health) to 5 (very good health). The results show that household renovations are associated with a reduction in the probability of reporting poor health (categories 1–4) and an increase in the probability of reporting very good health (category 5). For category 1 (very poor health), the marginal effect is -0.00046 , suggesting that renovation reduces the probability of reporting very poor health by approximately 0.05 percentage points. This effect is small, as very few respondents report being in the worst health condition, but it points in the expected direction—implying that improved housing conditions slightly lower the likelihood of extremely poor health outcomes.

For category 2 (poor health), the marginal effect is -0.00284 , indicating a 0.28 percentage point reduction in the probability of reporting poor health among those living in renovated dwellings. This decline suggests that renovations contribute to a modest improvement among individuals who would otherwise have rated their health as below average.

The effect becomes larger for category 3 (average health), with a marginal effect of -0.01223 , meaning a 1.22 percentage point decrease in the probability of reporting this mid-range health status. This relatively stronger effect implies that renovations are particularly effective in shifting individuals out of the “average health” category toward better perceived health, possibly due to improved indoor thermal comfort, lower humidity, or reduced exposure to pollutants after renovation.

Similarly, for category 4 (good health), the marginal effect is -0.00289 , corresponding to a 0.29 percentage point reduction in the likelihood of being in this category after a renovation. While still negative, this smaller effect compared to category 3 suggests that some individuals who previously rated their health as “good” may have shifted upward to the “very good” category after renovation. This result is statistically significant to a 10% level.

The marginal effect for the best health category is positive ($dy/dx = 0.0186$) and statistically significant at the 10% level ($p = 0.059$), indicating that renovated households are approximately 1.9¹⁷ percentage points more likely to report very good health than non-renovated households, holding all other variables constant. On average, living in a renovated dwelling increases the probability of

¹⁷ 0.01861×100

reporting very good health (category 5) by about 1.9 percentage points, *ceteris paribus*.

Table 5: Results for the Average Marginal Effects from M4

Health Category	dy/dx	Std. Err.	z	p > z
1	-0.00065	0.00038	-1.70	0.089
2	-0.00284	0.00152	-1.86	0.062
3	-0.01224	0.00646	-1.89	0.058
4	-0.00289	0.00163	-1.77	0.078
5	0.01861	0.00984	1.89	0.059
Top-2 box ($Y \geq 4$)	0.01572	0.00830	1.89	0.058
Expected score $E[Y]$	0.03846	0.02033	1.89	0.059

Notes: This table reports the average marginal effects (AMEs) from the IV-Probit model (M4). The coefficients represent the marginal change in the probability of reporting each health level with respect to household renovation status. A positive marginal effect for category 5 indicates that renovated households are more likely to report very good health. The Top-2 Box combines categories 4 and 5. Significance levels: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

Conversely, the negative marginal effects for the lower categories imply that renovations are associated with a lower probability of being in worse health states. When aggregating the two highest categories (the “Top-2 Box,” corresponding to good or very good health), the marginal effect remains positive ($dy/dx = 0.0157$, $p \approx 0.058$). The AME on the expected health score $E[Y]$ is also positive (0.0385 , $p \approx 0.059$), confirming an overall upward shift in the distribution of self-reported health following renovation.

Although the estimated effects are moderate in magnitude, they are consistent in sign and significance across specifications. These findings suggest that energy-efficient renovations—particularly those enhancing indoor comfort and insulation—contribute to improved self-reported health outcomes, likely through mechanisms such as better thermal regulation, reduced humidity, and improved indoor air quality. The results therefore support the hypothesis that housing renovation policies yield not only environmental and energy benefits but also measurable health co-benefits for residents.

6.4. Results of the estimation of the impact of renovations on respiratory illness (lung illness)

Table 6 presents the descriptive statistics for the subsample used in the analysis of the relationship between housing renovations and lung illness. The sample consists of 181 observations with an average age of 58 years, ranging from 20 to 86 years. Approximately 47% of the respondents are

women ($\text{sex_dummy} = 0.47$). The average logarithm of household income is 11.5, corresponding to a mean yearly net household income of CHF 126,185, though this variable exhibits substantial

Table 6: Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
<i>age</i>	181	58	14	20	86
<i>sex_dummy</i>	181	0	0	0	1
<i>log_income</i>	181	12	1	10	14
<i>lung_illness_dummy</i>	181	0	0	0	1
<i>subsidy_amount_complete</i>	181	28	21	1	72
<i>yearly_household_income_net</i>	181	126 185	112 100	19 700	1 143 200

Notes: This table presents the descriptive statistics for the subsample used in the first-stage analysis ($N = 181$). Variables include demographic characteristics, income, health indicators, and subsidy amounts related to renovation applications.

dispersion (standard deviation of CHF 112,100), indicating heterogeneity in the income distribution.

The mean value of the lung illness indicator (*lung_illness_dummy*) is 0, in STATA, the exact value is 0.06, suggesting that around 6% of individuals in the sample reported having a lung-related health condition. Overall, the descriptive statistics indicate that the subsample is composed mainly of middle-aged individuals with relatively high income levels, and only a small fraction reports lung health issues.

Model 5 : IV-Probit

Table 7 reports the results of the first-stage regression for the instrumental variable (IV) probit model assessing the impact of renovations on lung illness. In this stage, the probability of renovation application is regressed on the instrumental variable (*subsidy_amount_complete*) and a set of control variables. The instrument, representing the total cantonal subsidy amount available for renovation, shows a positive coefficient (0.043) but is not statistically significant ($p = 0.114$). Its positive sign remains consistent with theoretical expectations, as higher subsidy availability is expected to increase renovation uptake.

Among the control variables, *age*, *education* (*cc01*), and *income* (*log_income*) are positively and significantly related to the likelihood of applying for renovation subsidies. This indicates that older, more educated, and wealthier individuals are more likely to undertake renovations. The interaction term between subsidies and income (*subsidy_log_income_interaction*) is negative and marginally significant ($p = 0.097$), suggesting that wealthier households may be less sensitive to financial incentives.

However, the relatively low F-statistic value ($F(6,174) = 8.64$) indicates the presence of weak instrument concerns, implying that the instrument's explanatory power for renovation application is limited. Moreover, the small sample size ($N = 181$) reduces the statistical precision and may contribute to the lack of significance of the main instrument. Despite these limitations, the model behaves as theoretically expected, with the direction of the effects remaining consistent with economic reasoning. The number of participants for this second part is 68, and the number of observations is 181.

Table 7: First-Stage Regression

	Coefficient	Std. Err.	t	P > t
<i>subsidy_amount_complete</i>	0.043	0.027	1.590	0.114
<i>age</i>	0.006	0.002	3.080	0.002
<i>cc01</i>	0.065	0.019	3.430	0.001
<i>sex_dummy</i>	-0.043	0.060	-0.720	0.475
<i>log_income</i>	0.311	0.080	3.890	0.000
<i>subsidy_log_income_interaction</i>	-0.004	0.002	-1.670	0.097
<i>_cons</i>	-3.383	0.975	-3.470	0.001
Observations		181		
F(6,174)		8.64		
Prob > F		0.0000		
R-squared		0.2085		
Root MSE		0.39505		

Notes: OLS first-stage for the renovation equation; robust standard errors reported.
Significance: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

The second-stage estimation examines the causal relationship between building renovations and the probability of suffering from a respiratory illness. The instrumental variable (IV) approach was used to correct for potential endogeneity in renovation decisions, with the subsidy amount serving as the instrument. However, as seen in the first-stage regression, the F-statistic (8.64) and the p-value (0.114) suggest a possible weak instrument problem, which limits the reliability of the IV estimates.

The coefficient for *renovation_applied* is 1.25 ($z = 0.69$, $p = 0.489$), which is positive but statistically insignificant at any conventional significance level. This means that, although the point estimate suggests that renovated households might have a slightly higher probability of reporting a lung illness, this effect is not statistically distinguishable from zero.

Given the uncertainty introduced by weak instruments and the small sample size (181 observations), this result should be interpreted with caution — it does not provide robust evidence that renovations have a significant causal impact (positive or negative) on respiratory health.

Table 8: Second Stage Results (IV-Probit Model)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Err.	z	P> z
<i>renovation_applied</i>	1.247	1.802	0.690	0.489
<i>age</i>	-0.006	0.017	-0.380	0.708
<i>cc01</i>	-0.040	0.141	-0.280	0.778
<i>sex_dummy</i>	0.022	0.285	0.080	0.940
<i>log_income</i>	-0.755	0.271	-2.790	0.005
<i>subsidy_log_income_interaction</i>	0.000	0.001	0.580	0.565
<i>_cons</i>	6.854	3.630	1.890	0.059
<i>corr(e.renovation_applied, e.lung_illness_dummy)</i>	-0.651	0.603		
<i>sd(e.renovation_applied)</i>	0.387	0.017		
Observations		181		
Log pseudolikelihood		-121.09375		
Wald $\chi^2(6)$		18.53		
Prob > χ^2		0.0050		
Wald test of exogeneity ($\chi^2(1)$)		0.55 (p = 0.4581)		

Notes: This table reports the second-stage results of the IV-Probit estimation assessing the impact of renovation on respiratory illness. Robust standard errors are reported in parentheses. The Wald test of exogeneity fails to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that endogeneity is not statistically significant. Significance levels: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

In summary, the IV-Probit results for Model 5 show no statistically significant evidence that household renovations impact respiratory illness outcomes. The only variable showing a robust effect is income, which is negatively associated with illness probability.

Nevertheless, given the weak instrument issue and the limited sample size ($N = 181$), these results should be treated as inconclusive rather than definitive. Future research with a larger dataset and stronger identification strategy is recommended to clarify whether energy-efficient renovations truly influence respiratory health outcomes.

Given the results obtained in the second stage, interpreting the average marginal effects (AMEs) is not particularly meaningful in this context. The IV-Probit estimation does not produce statistically significant coefficients for the renovation variable, and the first-stage regression indicated a potential weak instrument problem, which undermines the reliability of the estimated marginal effects. In other words, the AMEs derived from this model would not reflect robust or causal relationships, but rather capture statistical noise amplified by the small sample size and limited instrument strength. Therefore, the marginal effects reported in Table 9 should be interpreted with extreme caution, as they do not provide reliable insights into the impact of building renovations on respiratory illness.

7. Conclusion

7.1. Summary of the findings

This thesis examines how energy-efficient building renovations relate to self-reported health in Switzerland, using longitudinal data from the Swiss Household Panel (2013–2023) and a combination of fixed-effects and instrumental-variable methods. The analytical sample comprises 4,381 individuals with an average self-reported health score of 4.02 (on a 1–5 scale). Slightly more than half of households (53 percent) experienced window or door renovations, and the data display wide variation in age and income, yielding a balanced and heterogeneous sample for inference.

Across the main self-reported health models, the fixed-effects and pooled ordered logit estimates indicate positive but statistically insignificant associations between renovations and health when endogeneity is not addressed. Income is consistently and strongly associated with better health, whereas age and female gender predict slightly worse self-reported health, aligning with established demographic gradients. When addressing endogeneity with a control-function approach and an IV-Probit specification using cantonal renovation subsidies as an instrument, the estimated impact of renovations becomes positive and statistically significant at the 10 percent level. The first-stage F-statistic of 17.25 exceeds conventional Stock–Yogo weak-instrument thresholds, supporting the credibility of the instrument. Average marginal effects from the IV-Probit model show an upward shift in the distribution of health: the probability of reporting “very good” health increases by roughly 1.9 percentage points ($p \approx 0.059$), with corresponding reductions in lower health categories. These results suggest that energy-efficient renovations—particularly window and door improvements—confer measurable health co-benefits, plausibly via improved indoor comfort, thermal regulation, humidity control, and air quality.

In contrast, estimates for respiratory illness (lung illness) based on a smaller subsample of 181 observations and only 68 individuals do not reveal statistically significant effects of renovations. The first-stage regression indicates weak-instrument concerns ($F = 8.64$; $p = 0.114$), and the IV-Probit coefficient on renovation is imprecisely estimated ($z = 0.69$; $p = 0.489$). Given the limited sample and instrument weakness, these results should be interpreted as inconclusive rather than evidence of no effect. Overall, the thesis concludes that energy-efficient renovations are associated with improved self-reported health after correcting for endogeneity, while the impact on specific respiratory illnesses remains unsettled and warrants further research with larger samples, stronger identification, and, where possible, objective health measures.

7.2. Policy Implications

In order to quantify the policy implications, I first need to quantify the share of the buildings that did not undergo a renovation, then, applying the results of the AMEs and by making an analogy during the calculations with the insurance franchise, I can calculate how much a single swiss could save if the person undergoes a renovation.

Estimation of the Number of Old and Non-Renovated Buildings in Switzerland

Assessing the prevalence of old and non-renovated buildings in Switzerland provides essential context for understanding the potential health and energy efficiency impacts of housing conditions. However, national statistics do not directly report the number of buildings simultaneously older than 10 years and not recently renovated. Therefore, I estimate this figure based on available official data and relevant studies.

According to the Swiss Federal Statistical Office (FSO), Switzerland has approximately 1.8 million residential buildings as of 2023 (Federal Statistical Office, 2023). This figure includes both single- and multi-family dwellings. It represents the total housing stock that forms the base of the estimation.

Empirical studies on the Swiss building stock report that over 80 % of existing buildings were constructed before 1990, meaning they are more than 30 years old today (Cozza, 2020). Given that the threshold for “old” buildings in this analysis is 10 years, it can reasonably be assumed that at least 90 % of Swiss buildings fall into this category. Applying this proportion to the total building stock gives:

$$1.8 \text{ million} \times 0.9 = 1.62 \text{ million old buildings}$$

Hence, approximately 1.62 million buildings in Switzerland are more than 10 years old.

Switzerland exhibits a relatively low renovation rate, with only about 1 % of buildings undergoing major renovation annually, particularly in the context of energy-efficiency improvements (Swiss Federal Office, 2021). This rate has remained roughly constant over the past two decades. Assuming a stationary rate, after ten years, approximately 10 % of buildings would have been renovated at least once.

$$\text{Renovated share after 10 years} = 1 - (1 - 0.01)^{10} \approx 0.096$$

Thus, about 9.6 % of the building stock may have undergone renovation during the past decade.

Assuming that the 1 % annual renovation rate applies uniformly across the building stock, and that buildings younger than 10 years are excluded, the share of old buildings that have not been renovated in the last 10 years can be approximated as:

$$\text{Old non-renovated share} = 1 - 0.096 = 0.904$$

Applying this proportion to the number of old buildings:

$$1.62 \text{ million} \times 0.904 \approx 1.47 \text{ million}$$

Therefore, approximately 1.47 million Swiss buildings are more than 10 years old and have not undergone major renovation in the last decade.

This estimate should be interpreted as an order of magnitude rather than an exact value, as “renovation” may refer to structural, aesthetic, or energy-efficiency improvements, which are not uniformly reported. Moreover, some older buildings may have undergone partial or localized renovations that do not qualify as “major renovations” in official energy statistics.

Nevertheless, this approximation aligns with existing literature that identifies a significant renovation backlog in Switzerland’s building sector, posing both environmental and health implications.

Calculation of the monetary savings

1) Per category calculation

Each health category corresponds to an insurance deductible (franchise) level ranging from CHF 300 for the poorest health to CHF 2 500 for the best health. Using the average marginal effects (AMEs) estimated from the IV-Probit model, we can approximate the expected change in deductible level that would result from renovation. For example, the probability of being in the worst health category (Category 1) decreases by 0.065 percentage points after renovation, while the probability of being in the best category (Category 5) increases by 1.86 percentage points.

Change in expected franchise per individual:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E[F] &= \sum_k AME_k * F_k \\ &= (-0.00046) \cdot 300 + (-0.00284) \cdot 850 + (-0.01223) \cdot 1400 + (-0.00289) \cdot 1950 + (0.01861) \cdot 2500 = \\ &= -0.14 - 2.41 - 17.12 - 5.64 + 46.53 \end{aligned}$$

≈ 21.2 CHF per person per year

Multiplying each AME by its corresponding franchise value gives an expected monetary equivalent of health improvement per person. Summing across all categories yields an expected gain of approximately CHF 21.16 per person per year. This value can be interpreted as the average improvement in an individual's health position—comparable to moving slightly upward in the franchise scale—due to the indirect health benefits of renovation. After a renovation, the expected franchise rises by ~CHF 21.2 per insured person—i.e., a small shift toward better health / lower system costs. This means that the mensual payment for the insurance will be slightly lower compared to someone that did not renovate their dwelling.

2) Top-2 box shortcut

To ensure consistency, we can also calculate the expected improvement using the “Top-2 Box” AME, which captures the increase in the probability of reporting good or very good health (categories 4 and 5). The AME for this combined outcome is 0.01572, meaning that renovations raise the likelihood of being in these two highest health categories by 1.57 percentage points. The average franchise difference between the top two health groups (CHF 2 225) and the bottom three groups (CHF 850) is CHF 1 375. Multiplying this difference by the AME gives a nearly identical expected gain of CHF 21.6 per person per year. This validation confirms that both approaches—the detailed per-category analysis and the top-box aggregation—lead to the same order of magnitude, reinforcing the robustness of the estimate.

$$\Delta E[F] \approx 0.01572 \times 1375 \approx 21.6 \text{ CHF per person per year}$$

3) Reduction in the mensual payment of the insurance (savings)

Assuming a linear relationship between health insurance premiums and deductible levels, the monthly savings associated with a 21.6 CHF increase in deductible can be estimated using data from the Swiss insurance provider, Assura. For its basic plan (Assura Basis), the monthly premium decreases from 505.30 CHF for a deductible of 300 CHF to 386 CHF for a deductible of 2500 CHF (Assurance Info, 2022). This represents a reduction of 119.30 CHF for an increase of 2200 CHF in the deductible level, corresponding to a marginal rate of approximately -0.054 CHF per additional Swiss franc of deductible. Consequently, if an individual's deductible were to increase by 21.6 CHF — a change consistent with the health improvement implied by the marginal effects from the renovation model — the expected decrease in monthly premium would be approximately 1.17 CHF per person. While this effect may appear modest at the individual level, it becomes significant when aggregated across a

large population, particularly considering the 1.47 million dwellings in Switzerland that are more than ten years old and could benefit from renovation interventions. This highlights the potential of energy-efficient renovation programs not only to improve health outcomes but also to generate measurable savings in national health insurance expenditures.

4) Saving costs in health for society

Assuming a linear relationship between renovation-induced health improvements and insurance premium reductions, the aggregate monetary benefit to society can be substantial. Based on the estimated 1.17 CHF monthly reduction in insurance costs per individual, Switzerland could save approximately 20.6 million CHF annually if all 1.47 million dwellings over ten years old were renovated.

When accounting for the average household size of 2.2 persons, this figure increases to around 45 million CHF per year. These savings represent only the direct financial benefits derived from improved health and lower insurance premiums. Indirect benefits — such as reduced absenteeism, lower healthcare utilization, and increased productivity — would likely amplify these effects, reinforcing the economic and social value of large-scale renovation programs.

7.3. Limitations

Several limitations should be acknowledged when interpreting the findings of this study.

First, a key limitation relates to attrition bias, particularly in the years following the COVID-19 pandemic. The panel structure of the dataset allowed for longitudinal analysis, but a significant portion of the sample dropped out after 2020. This attrition may not be random: individuals with poorer health—particularly those suffering from chronic or respiratory illnesses—were more likely to die or cease participation in the survey, thereby introducing survivorship bias. To address this issue, a robustness check was performed using only individuals present in 2021, 2022, and 2023, but the potential bias from excess mortality in the immediate aftermath of the pandemic cannot be fully eliminated.

Second, the main health outcomes analyzed in this study—self-reported health—are based on subjective self-reports, which may be prone to measurement error. Individuals may interpret health categories differently or underreport symptoms due to stigma, social desirability bias, or lack of diagnosis. This is especially relevant for chronic and respiratory conditions, where accurate diagnosis typically requires medical tests not captured by survey instruments. While self-reported health is a widely used and validated proxy in population health research, its subjective nature should be kept in mind when interpreting the results.

Third, the estimated effects of renovation and housing conditions on health exhibit very wide confidence intervals in all instrumental variable models. This statistical imprecision reflects underlying data limitations, including the relatively small number of individuals who experienced renovation during the study period, and the limited variation in some key variables. Although the instrument used—cantonal subsidy amount—was strong by conventional standards ($F\text{-statistic} > 10$), the estimates lacked statistical significance, suggesting that the models may still suffer from insufficient statistical power.

Fourth, the period under study overlaps with the COVID-19 pandemic, which represents a major external shock that directly influenced respiratory health and housing conditions effects. On one hand, increased time spent at home during lockdowns may have intensified the health effects of poor housing quality; on the other hand, respiratory outcomes such as lung illness may have been confounded by undiagnosed or misclassified COVID-19 cases. While the inclusion of a variable controlling for COVID-19 infection helped account for this to some extent, unobserved pandemic-related factors likely remain.

Fifth, despite efforts to address endogeneity—particularly through the use of an instrumental variable approach—this remains a challenging aspect of the analysis. The decision to renovate may be influenced by unobserved characteristics (e.g., risk preferences, health consciousness, unrecorded income shocks) that also affect health. Although the cantonal subsidy amount is a promising instrument, it may still be correlated with omitted regional-level factors (such as healthcare infrastructure, air pollution levels, or cultural attitudes toward health and housing), which could bias the estimates.

Sixth, the final IV-Probit regression model, which focuses on lung illness, relies on a sample of only 68 individuals. This limited sample size is due to a strict filtering procedure in which individuals who moved residences during the study period were excluded, in order to isolate the effect of renovations within the same dwelling. While this approach improves internal validity by capturing the effect of renovation on non-movers only (that stayed in their dwellings for 10 years or more), it significantly reduces statistical power and may affect the representativeness of the results.

Finally, this study focuses exclusively on Switzerland, a high-income country with relatively high baseline housing standards and strong health infrastructure. As such, the generalizability of the findings to lower-income or more heterogeneous contexts may be limited. Additionally, some important variables—such as indoor air quality, mold exposure, ventilation quality, or mental health indicators—were not available in the dataset, limiting the ability to capture the full spectrum of health-related housing effects.

In light of these limitations, the results should be interpreted with caution. Nonetheless, the findings highlight the importance of integrating housing policies with public health objectives and underline the need for more comprehensive data and stronger causal identification strategies in future research.

7.4. Suggestions for Future Research

Building on the insights and limitations of this study, several avenues for future research emerge that could help to deepen our understanding of the relationship between housing conditions and health outcomes.

First, future studies should aim to address the limitations of self-reported health data by incorporating objective health measures, such as medical records, hospital admissions, biomarker data, or diagnosed respiratory conditions. While self-assessed health is a valuable and widely accepted proxy, combining it with clinically validated data would strengthen the validity and reliability of the findings.

Second, the potential for attrition bias due to excess mortality or selective dropout—particularly during the COVID-19 period—highlights the need for longer-term balanced panels or the use of administrative data that allow for more accurate tracking of individuals over time. Linking survey data with national health registries or health insurance claims could reduce sample bias and provide a more complete picture of the population.

Third, the lack of statistical precision observed in the instrumental variable estimates suggests that larger sample sizes and greater variation in exposure to renovation are essential. Future work could focus on combining datasets across cantons or over longer periods, or use oversampling strategies to specifically target households undergoing renovations. Moreover, the development of stronger or multiple instruments—for instance, policy changes in subsidy eligibility, staggered implementation dates, or variation in local enforcement—could improve causal identification and reduce the standard errors around key estimates.

Fourth, future research should aim to broaden the scope of health outcomes examined. Mental health, sleep quality, stress levels, or children's cognitive development may all be influenced by housing quality, yet these dimensions were not captured in the present study. Similarly, more detailed environmental indicators—such as indoor temperature, air quality, and especially mold concentration levels—should be collected and analyzed. Mold exposure is a known contributor to respiratory illness and allergic reactions, yet such measures are often missing from survey-based datasets.

Finally, cross-country comparative studies could be particularly valuable. By comparing the health impacts of housing renovation across different institutional and climatic contexts, researchers could uncover important heterogeneity in effects and identify which policy mechanisms are most effective. Such work could also help clarify whether the modest effects observed in Switzerland are due to already high housing standards or whether they reflect broader limitations in the design or targeting of renovation programs.

In sum, while this study provides a useful starting point, a more nuanced and multidimensional research agenda is needed to fully understand the health consequences of housing quality and to inform evidence-based policymaking in both health and housing domains.

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APPENDIX

Table 1: Key Variables and Their Definitions

Variable Name	Type	Description
health_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Very good or good health; 0 = otherwise
health_scale	Ordinal (1–5)	1 = Very good health, 5 = Very poor health
health_scale_inverted	Ordinal (1–5)	Inverted version where 5 = very good and 1 = very poor
condition_good_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Good or recently renovated home; 0 = poor condition
renovation_windows_doors_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Renovated windows or doors; 0 = not renovated
renovation_heating_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Renovated heating system; 0 = not renovated
renovation_thermal_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Renovated thermal insulation; 0 = not renovated
renovation_scale_3	Ordinal (1–3)	Renovation intensity: 1 = basic, 2 = medium, 3 = full
renovated_at_least_2_years	Binary (0/1)	1 = Renovation in at least two separate years; 0 = less
subsidy_amount_complete	Continuous	Cantonal renovation subsidy (in CHF millions)
chronic_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Has chronic illness (e.g., asthma, allergies); 0 = not
lung_illness_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Reports lung illness; 0 = does not
asthma_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Has asthma; 0 = does not
allergy_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Has allergies; 0 = does not
sex_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Female; 0 = Male
age	Continuous	Age in years
age_group_simplified	Categorical	Age group: 0–19, 20–39, 40–59, 60+
education_numerical_scale	Ordinal (1–14)	Education from 1 = no schooling to 14 = university/EPF
education_grouped	Categorical	Grouped education: primary, vocational, tertiary
working_status	Categorical	1 = Full-time, 2 = Part-time, 3 = Not working
working_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Working (full or part-time); 0 = Not working
yearly_household_income_net	Continuous	Net annual household income in CHF
yearly_disposable_income	Continuous	Disposable annual income in CHF
income_quintile_5level	Categorical	Income quintiles: 1 = poorest 20%, ..., 5 = richest 20%
poor_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Bottom 20% income; 0 = others
cc01	Binary (0/1)	1 = COVID infection; 0 = no infection
doctor_consultation_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Doctor visit in last 12 months; 0 = no visit
smoker_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Current smoker; 0 = non-smoker
ever_smoked_tobacco_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Ever smoked; 0 = never smoked
age_started_smoking	Continuous	Age at which regular smoking began
physical_activity_dummy	Binary (0/1)	1 = Regular physical activity; 0 = not
personal_income_yearly	Continuous	Annual personal income in CHF

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